

Building the EU Cancer and Health Genomics Platform

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Deliverable 12.2 – Citizen and Patient Perspectives on Oncogenomic Data Reuse

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Summary

This deliverable formulates ethical recommendations for a trustworthy framework for genomic data reuse in oncology based on the perspectives of patients, citizens, and Can.Heal professionals. It highlights areas where the values of the general public and professionals align, yet also where they might differ, indicating ethical points of discussion to be considered in the EU Cancer and Health Genomics Platform. Every chapter is built around a visual that captures the dynamics between the different perspectives.

Context and Objectives

Can.Heal was created to bridge gaps in cancer genomics across clinical, research, and public health domains through an EU-wide oncogenomics platform. As the EU shifts toward personalized medicine, massive amounts of genomic and health data must be managed to respect privacy while enabling broad data reuse. However, these technologies introduce complex ethical, legal, and societal challenges, necessitating a framework that incorporates patient and citizen input alongside professional standards.

This deliverable, led by Sciensano's ELSI Unit (Ethics, Legal, and Societal Issues), forms part of Work Package 12.2, specifically focuses on understanding and integrating the perspectives of patients, citizens, and professionals. It tackles three main areas:

1. Privacy in genomic data reuse;
2. Reuse of genomic data for clinical purposes;
3. Ethical considerations related to incidental findings.

Methodology and Engagement

To formulate recommendations that align with public and expert expectations, the deliverable draws insights from a literature review of public engagement initiatives in genomics and the Can.Heal Ethics Stakeholder Workshop. The literature review identified key patient and citizen values, needs, and concerns, while the workshop allowed stakeholders to compare and discuss these findings with professional perspectives. The recommendations are addressed to any expert in oncogenomics, as well as EU and national health policymakers.

Key Findings and Ethical Implications

Privacy in Genomic Data Reuse

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Privacy concerns are central to genomic data reuse, especially in oncology, where the sensitivity and identifiability of data affect patient trust. Patients and citizens view genomic data as intimately linked to their identities, considering privacy protections essential to prevent misuse. This population often favors an exceptionalist view, seeing genomic data as uniquely sensitive. In contrast, Can.Heal professionals typically approach privacy through the lens of data security and regulatory compliance, emphasizing the need for stringent safeguards to prevent misuse rather than focusing on re-identifiability.

Both groups agree that privacy is a dynamic concept that should adapt to the context and intended use of the data. For instance, patients and citizens accept pseudonymization techniques in clinical and research contexts where anonymization may limit the societal and individual benefits of data. Yet, outside these trusted settings, lay participants often prefer stronger privacy measures to prevent potential harms, such as discrimination or stigmatization.

Reuse of Genomic Data for Clinical Purposes

In clinical settings, genomic data has a dual role as both an individual and a collective asset. While patients value autonomy and the right to control data reuse, they also acknowledge the societal benefits, such as aiding similar cases or supporting future research. Balancing personal rights with collective good emerges as a central ethical consideration. Citizens support data reuse when aligned with values like solidarity and altruism and expect opportunities to be informed or involved in data governance to ensure transparency and maintain trust.

Can.Heal professionals emphasize the need for interoperability between clinical and research domains, where identifiable and de-identified data must flow efficiently to maximize personalized care benefits. However, the challenge lies in reconciling this need for data fluidity with robust consent procedures that respect autonomy. A shared decision-making approach is proposed, where professionals and patients can discuss data reuse options and agree on terms that respect both individual preferences and clinical needs.

Incidental Findings and Ethical Considerations

Incidental findings—unexpected results unrelated to a primary diagnosis—pose additional ethical complexities. Patients and citizens generally support the disclosure of relevant incidental findings but desire control over the scope and manner of sharing this information. They also express concerns about the potential emotional and familial impact of receiving incidental findings, particularly when related to untreatable or stigmatizing conditions.

Can.Heal professionals suggest protocols to manage incidental findings in a way that respects patient preferences, including informed consent procedures that allow patients to specify what types of findings they wish to be informed about. They agree on the importance of transparent communication and ongoing support, such as genetic counseling, to help individuals understand and process incidental findings within a clinical context.

Recommendations for a Trustworthy Genomic Data Framework

The deliverable translates these findings into recommendations to create a trustworthy and ethically sound framework for genomic data reuse. The recommendations balance privacy protections, data utility, and public trust, advocating for:

- 1. Context-Dependent Privacy Measures:** Genomic data reuse should adopt privacy measures that align with the specific context, balancing the need for data fluidity with privacy safeguards.
- 2. Appropriate Consent Mechanisms:** Consent procedures should respect patient autonomy while minimizing administrative burdens on clinicians and researchers. Opt-out mechanisms are overall preferable, but most importantly, there needs to be clarity about when data can be accessed without the need for consent.
- 3. Management of Incidental Findings:** Patients and citizens should have control over the type of incidental findings they wish to receive. Counseling and clear communication from clinicians are needed to help individuals make informed choices and mitigate potential distress or confusion related to incidental findings.
- 4. Stakeholder Engagement and Transparency:** Building and maintaining public trust requires continuous engagement with citizens and patients, ensuring they feel informed and valued in data governance processes. Transparency about data practices, including limitations of privacy protections, is vital. Integrating stakeholder input through public engagement initiatives and advisory boards can help adapt policies in response to societal shifts and technological advances.
- 5. Safeguarding Vulnerable Populations:** Special protections should be afforded to vulnerable populations, such as rare disease patients and ethnic minorities, who face additional ethical and societal barriers. Ensuring equitable access to genomic medicine and preventing discrimination based on genomic data are essential for fostering inclusive, fair data reuse practices.

Conclusion

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This deliverable highlights the need for a flexible, ethically robust framework for genomic data reuse in oncology that aligns with patient and citizen values while enabling the EU Cancer and Health Genomics Platform to achieve its full potential. By embedding privacy, consent, transparency, and ethical protections within genomic data practices, Can.Heal can establish a model of trustworthy genomic data reuse that supports personalized medicine advancements and builds public confidence.

Introduction

Can.Heal: Building the EU Cancer and Health Genomics Platform

Scientific progress and the expansion of genomic technologies have accelerated the shift from traditional care to a more personalized and preventive approach to medicine. The collection, storage, and processing of large amounts of genomic data, combined with other health data, has enabled research to understand diseases' origin and development, pharmacogenomics to conceive more targeted treatments, public health policies to increase the quality of life while reducing public expenditure, and healthcare professionals to improve patient care pathways and preventive measures¹. This revolution concerns many diseases, but cancer in particular. Since cancer is classified as the second leading cause of death in the European population, Europe has generated colossal investments to reduce its mortality rate². This fight against cancer requires harnessing the power of genomic data beyond the individual context of primary use and ensuring that society as a whole benefits from it. To unleash this power of genomic data reuse, building synergies between the clinical, research, and public health contexts is critical.

The European consortium Can.Heal³ has been established to meet this need. By gathering the expertise of 17 Member States, Can.Heal aims to improve prevention, diagnosis, and treatment in oncology through personalized medicine and genomics in the clinical, research, and public health contexts. It addresses the gap of multi-stakeholder coordination in healthcare policies and innovative clinical and research programs across Europe in the field of oncogenomics. By investigating use cases, sharing expertise, stimulating common reflection, and building knowledge translation in areas as diverse as biobanking, polygenic risk scores, liquid biopsy, early detection, and treatment follow-up, Can.Heal builds the bridge between key stakeholders, such as academic researchers, public health institutes, healthcare professionals, policymakers, and the general public (patients and citizens). The final outputs of the 14 work packages (see <https://canheal.eu/project/> for more information) will help these stakeholders tackle the many challenges of personalized medicine in oncogenomics by providing recommendations on, for instance, patient and citizen access to personalized prevention, diagnosis, and treatment, effective policies and strategies in cancer prevention, and ethical and legal

¹ Kreeftenberg LL, Henneman L, Ket JCF, et al. (2024). Engagement of patients and the public in personalised prevention in Europe using genomic information: A scoping review. *Frontier in Public Health* 12: 1456853.

² Guillot JD (2022). Fighting cancer in the EU: Statistics and action. *European Parliament*, 17 February. Available at https://www.europarl.europa.eu/pdfs/news/expert/2020/2/story/20200131STO71517/20200131STO71517_en.pdf (accessed 21 October 2024).

³ Can.Heal (n.d.) Building the EU cancer and public health genomics platform. Available at: <https://canheal.eu/project/> (accessed 8 November 2024).

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issues regarding the reuse of genomic data across Europe via the ‘EU Cancer and Health Genomics Platform’⁴.

The creation of this European cancer genomic platform for effective data reuse in interconnected contexts raises numerous ethical, legal, and societal issues that require the engagement of the general public, whose contribution is essential to making this ambitious project a reality. While current European legislations, such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the European Health Data Space (EHDS) regulation, constitute a well-structured starting point, further ethical and legal reflection is needed to ensure that genomic data reuse remains trustworthy. This responsibility is carried out by Can.Heal’s WP12, “Law, Ethics and Citizen Engagement”.

This WP12 is divided into two tasks:

- *WP12.1: Ethical and Legal Compliance Recommendations for Data Governance.* Led by the Luxembourg National Data Service (LNDS), this first task aims to develop ethical and legal data governance for cancer genomics, including clearly defining the purpose(s) for which data will be processed, i.e. data sharing and secondary use for research, public policy, and clinical purposes (e.g. to care other patients).
- *WP12.2: Citizen and Patient Perspectives on Oncogenomic Data Reuse.* Led by Sciensano's ELSI Unit (Ethics, Legal, and Societal Issues), this second task aims to formulate ethical recommendations for a trustworthy framework for genomic data reuse in oncology based on the perspectives of the general public (patients and citizens) primarily, but also oncogenomic professionals of the Can.Heal consortium (academic researchers, health professionals, and members of public health institutes). More specifically, the focus will be on identifying common grounds and potential conflicts of values between the lay and the expert perspectives with regard to the three topics of interest to the consortium: 1. Privacy, 2. Genomic data reuse for clinical purposes, and 3. Incidental findings. The recommendations are addressed to any expert in oncogenomics, as well as EU and national health policymakers.

The present deliverable is the result of the work produced in WP12.2.

WP12.2: Citizen and Patient Perspectives on Oncogenomic Data Reuse

The successful implementation of personalized medicine substantially depends on the support of patients and citizens. In the clinical context, it is in the interest of healthcare professionals that patients welcome the use of genomic sequencing techniques, are adequately informed about the implications

⁴ Can.Heal (n.d.) Can.Heal project. Available at: <https://canheal.eu/project/> (accessed 14 November 2024).

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of genomic data reused for both their personalized care and to help similar cases of disease, and are empowered in their health management beyond the confines of hospitals. In the research domain, patients' and healthy citizens' participation is vital to advance scientific knowledge⁵. At the governance level, a population that feels considered and respected in political decision-making is more likely to adhere to prevention programs and adopt a solidarity mindset in sharing data to feed the system and help other patients who could benefit from it⁶.

The cooperation of the general public is hardly achievable without public engagement. Public engagement is a cornerstone in building trust between lay and expert stakeholders. This requires the investigation of lay people's values, needs, and concerns and the creation of a mutual understanding through open and transparent dialogues⁷⁻⁸⁻⁹. The Can.Heal consortium—composed of academic researchers, health professionals, and members of public health institutes—must apprehend what motivates citizens and patients to contribute to personalized medicine or what stops them from doing so to adapt data governance to their preferences and experiences. Yet, to ensure meaningful engagement, one should pay attention to two aspects of stakeholder management. Firstly, when various stakeholders discuss an issue, they often interpret the subject differently due to their differing backgrounds, interests, personal experiences, and the language used (particularly in genomics, where technical jargon is commonplace). If not managed appropriately, such a situation can lead to misunderstanding, confusion, frustration, and even unintentional misplaced actions. This could be avoided by ensuring that stakeholders are talking about the same thing and are at the same level of discussion. Secondly, stakeholders often have conflicting agendas and, hence, they frequently disagree about which priorities to implement. Nevertheless, they may share more values, needs, and concerns than it might first appear. Given that values, needs, and concerns are the driving forces behind important decisions, it is essential to look beyond divergent priorities and agendas and, instead, investigate the values, needs, and concerns of both the general public and oncogenomic professionals and see where they might correspond or differ. Only then, an effective collaboration and long-term relationships of trust can emerge.

⁵ Horton R and Lucassen A (2023). Ethical considerations in research with genomic data. *The New Bioethics* 29 (1): 37-51.

⁶ Kreeftenberg, Henneman, Ket, et al. (2024).

⁷ Bilodeau E, Cumyn A, Ménard J-F, et al. (2024). Utilisations secondaires des données de santé : Impacts de la transparence. *Canadian Journal of Bioethics* 7 (2-3) : 118-137.

⁸ Reed MS, Merkle BG, Cook EJ, et al. (2024). Reimagining the language of engagement in a post-stakeholder world. *Sustainability Science* 19: 1481-1490.

⁹ Fox B and Martschenko DO (2023). Rethinking the “public” and rethinking “engagement”. *The American Journal of Bioethics* 23 (7): 66-68.

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In line with these objectives, the present deliverable aims to answer the following questions regarding genomic data reuse in oncology:

- 1) What are the values, needs, and concerns of the general public (patients and citizens), on the one hand, and oncogenomic professionals (Can.Heal consortium), on the other hand? What are the common grounds they share, and what are the potential conflicts that may arise?
- 2) How do patients, citizens, and Can.Heal professionals interpret important values at stake? How can these interpretations be integrated into a mutual understanding?
- 3) How could shared values be translated into potential agreements or a consensus about actions to implement?
- 4) How can we manage remaining conflicts of values to avoid damaging the trust between patients, citizens, and oncogenomic professionals?

Work Performed in WP12.2

To be able to answer these questions, the perspectives of the general public and Can.Heal professionals have been collected and investigated through two main activities:

- 1) A literature review on public engagement initiatives in genomics to identify the starting points for developing an ethical framework for trustworthy reuse of genomic data.
- 2) A stakeholder workshop to integrate the perspectives of Can.Heal professionals in the ethical framework and compare their input with the results of the literature review on patient and citizen perspectives.

These two activities are part of the broader process of WP12.2, described in Figure 1.

FIGURE 1 - Timeline of WP12.2

Literature Review of Public Engagement Initiatives in Genomics

The objective of the literature review on patient and citizen engagement initiatives was to identify their central values, needs, and concerns when discussing the ethical, legal, and societal issues in genomics. Based on this review, overviews of lay values, needs, and concerns have been created to help Can.Heal professionals understand what matters to patients and citizens in genomics and, more specifically, in relation to the topics of interest to the consortium (privacy, genomic data reuse for clinical purposes, and incidental findings). These overviews of lay values, needs, and concerns summarize and structure general trends across selected publications on patient and citizen engagement initiatives.

To constitute the corpus of the literature review, publications that met the following criteria have been selected:

- Citizen and patient engagement initiatives conducted all over Europe. Besides, some initiatives from the UK, USA, Canada, Australia, and Switzerland have been included since they represent relevant and high-quality engagement initiatives on genomics.
- Qualitative and quantitative methods collecting the opinions of the general population, including citizens and cancer patients of various age groups (including children and teenagers), levels of education, socio-economic backgrounds, and cultural and religious beliefs. Beyond this broad targeted audience, initiatives that engage underrepresented groups, such as rare disease patients and ethnic minorities have also been included because of the specific challenges and obstacles they face in personalized medicine and genomics.
- Publications from the last ten years (2013-2023) but as recent as possible since oncogenomics and personalized medicine are rapidly evolving. The time frame limit is justified by the fact that the American College of Medical Genetics and Genomics (ACMG) published recommendations on reporting incidental findings in 2013, generating many reactions, including patient engagement initiatives on related ethical questions.

In total, 45 publications have been selected, including 22 about citizen engagement initiatives and 23 about patient engagement initiatives, organized in France, Belgium, Denmark, Australia, Italy, Germany, Serbia, Romania, the Netherlands, Greece, Portugal, Slovakia, Iceland, Czech Republic, Ireland, Switzerland, Canada, the UK, and the USA, or simultaneously in several or all EU Members States. Annex 1 lists the publications included in the literature review. For each publication, a focus was maintained on the results section since this described the opinions of patients and citizens as closely as possible to the data. It must be noted that this literature review is neither systematic nor exhaustive, and its relevance is limited to the context of Can.Heal.

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The overviews of the values, needs, and concerns of patients and citizens in genomics in the clinical, research, and public health contexts were created using MIRO¹⁰. MIRO is a creative and collaborative software tool that, i.a., allows data to be organized into visual structures to clarify complex links between all components. Figure 2 below shows an example of visual structure in MIRO resulting from the literature review.

FIGURE 2 - Example of a visual structuring of the results in MIRO

The visual structure on the left illustrates the interactions between the values of patients and citizens regarding the use of genomic data for research. The structure on the right explains the dynamics between their various needs in the same context.

MIRO also provides many opportunities to engage stakeholders online through interactive exercises. Hence, this tool was also used for the stakeholder workshop involving experts of the Can.Heal consortium.

Can.Heal Ethics Stakeholder Workshop

On Tuesday, 17 October 2023, an Ethics Stakeholder Workshop was organized to present the results of the literature reviews to the Can.Heal consortium and to integrate the perspectives of oncogenomic professionals into the ethical framework for genomic data reuse. In total, 43 Can.Heal

¹⁰ <https://miro.com/>

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professionals engaged online in an interactive, three-hour discussion on three topics: (1) Privacy, (2) Genomic data reuse for clinical purposes, and (3) Incidental findings.

During the general assembly (Berlin) preceding the workshop, Can.Heal members were asked to vote for the three questions they wanted to discuss at the workshop (one question per topic) among a list of eleven questions. They voted for the following questions:

- 1) Privacy: How can we balance data de-identification with the potential benefits of returning results to patients (and their relatives)?
- 2) Reuse of genomic data for clinical purposes: How can we respect individual rights in data reuse (e.g. consent, right to be forgotten) without overburdening researchers and clinicians?
- 3) Incidental findings: Should incidental findings be limited as much as possible, or should we evolve toward a practice of secondary findings in some contexts?

Each of the three questions was discussed through interactive exercises following the same structure:

- 1) As a starting point for discussions, the main values, needs, and concerns of patients and citizens identified in the literature were presented with regard to the topic at stake.
- 2) The perspectives of Can.Heal professionals were explored by asking for their opinions and practical experiences regarding ethical and legal issues related to each topic. They were asked to identify key elements to consider when building a legal and ethical framework for genomic data reuse to fight cancer in Europe.
- 3) Finally, these key elements were translated into suggestions for best practices.

After the workshop, the inputs made by participants on the MIRO board were verified and, if needed, completed by listening to the recording of the discussions. Afterwards, the recording was deleted to respect the participants' privacy. All participants received a link to the MIRO board with the collaborative results of the workshop to verify that the results accurately represent their perspectives and provide any kind of feedback, if needed. In addition to the stakeholder workshop, meetings with representatives of two Can.Heal use cases were organized to clarify some technical aspects of current genomic data reuse practices and to ensure that the recommendations within this deliverable will be helpful on a practical level.

Results

The results of the literature review on public engagement were compared with the outputs from the Can.Heal workshop to investigate potential conflicts of values, common grounds, or complementary vision on the ethical issues in genomics between the general public and professionals in oncogenomics. For each of the three topics on which this deliverable focuses (1. Privacy, 2. Genomic data reuse for clinical purposes, 3. Incidental findings), visuals were created to translate the perspectives of patients, citizens, and Can.Heal professionals into systems of values and ethical considerations regarding genomic data reuse in the clinical, research, and public health contexts. These visuals mirror how lay and expert stakeholders think about genomic data at the individual and societal levels and illustrate how their values interact. Analyzing the underlying representations behind the discourse of each stakeholder helps better understand their perspective and facilitates earnest dialogue.

All the statements made in this *Results* section are based either on the literature review on public engagement when developing the perspective of patients and citizens or on the output of the Can.Heal stakeholder workshop when explaining the perspective of professionals in oncogenomics. Nevertheless, the sections *Discussion on Ethical Implications* and *Recommendations* allow for some further ethical reflection.

Privacy in the Reuse of Genomic Data

Introduction

Finding the right balance between, on the one hand, respecting privacy and, on the other hand, the individual and societal benefits of massively reusing genomic data is a major challenge in oncogenomics and personalized medicine¹¹. To solve this challenging tension, one should first understand how the reuse of genomic data impacts privacy. This first section of the deliverable will explore how patients, citizens, and Can.Heal professionals think about privacy in genomics and how their perspectives might share common grounds or create potential conflicts of values that must be addressed to preserve trust in genomic data reuse.

¹¹ Kilgus T, Patecka A, Schurig T, et al. (2024). Creating value from the secondary use of health data: International examples, best practices, and opportunities to scale. *Communications of the Association for Information Systems* 55: 507-534.

FIGURE 3 - Privacy in genomic data reuse

Divergent Conceptions of the Link Between Individuals and their Genomic Data

Comparing the literature review on patients' and citizens' perspectives and the outputs from the Can.Heal ethics workshop highlights that citizens, patients, and Can.Heal professionals do not have the same approach to privacy in genomics. Yet, they also share many values and common grounds. Consequently, their perspectives on privacy in genomic data reuse complement each other.

As a starting point, they understand the link between individuals and their genomic data differently.

On their side, patients and citizens establish a close link between their genome and their identity, considering that their DNA tells a lot about who they are in the past (genealogy), present (diagnosis of genetic disorders), and future (predispositions to diseases). As a result, they regard genomic information as an intimate part of themselves, which they also share with their relatives. Nevertheless, most of the time, patients and citizens do not reduce their identity to their genome and vice-versa. They recognize the influence of non-genetic factors on their identity formation, such as socio-cultural determinants (education). Participants of public engagement initiatives frequently claim that people are more than their genetic makeup as complex human beings and should, therefore, not be reduced to it. Likewise, some understand the multifactorial nature of genetic diseases' development. Genetic determinism remains a minor belief that should be addressed through better education, for instance, on the probabilistic nature of genetic testing results and the evolutive translations of genotype to phenotype.

On their side, Can.Heal professionals approach the link between individuals and their genomic data through the lens of identification, which they consider not problematic in itself. Depending on how data are (re)used, identification can generate both benefits (e.g. returning results to patients, personalized medicine) and harms (privacy breaches and any misuse of sensitive information). That is why the trustworthiness of data users is of utmost importance and goes beyond technical security measures and safeguards to protect the identity of data subjects. In this regard, some Can.Heal professionals criticize the GDPR for tackling the problem of privacy mainly from the angle of identifying data subjects, which will be unavoidable in some circumstances when massively reusing genomic data for personalized medicine, whereas the focus should be on tackling the misuse of identifiable data.

The Continuum of Sensitivity of Genomic Data

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Patients, citizens, and Can.Heal professionals all view genomic data as sensitive information that requires adequate protection. The degree of sensitivity they assign to it varies according to a continuum, ranging from an exceptionalist to a non-exceptionalist approach to genomics.

The exceptionalist approach considers genomic data to be the most sensitive data, requiring the highest level of protection. While one could criticize the exceptional status of DNA as overestimated, the values and ethical arguments underlying it should not be ignored. First, DNA allows for the identification of individuals in a unique manner (citizens compare it to a barcode). Second, genomic data are of great interest to many professionals for a variety of purposes, meaning their reuse can affect individuals in multiple ways. Third, genomic information is shared with relatives who can be impacted negatively by data misuse. Besides, some citizens see their genomic information as the last piece of privacy still protected in a society of extensive data processing.

The non-exceptionalist approach recognizes DNA as being as sensitive as other personal data yet without exceptional status. Proponents among the public tend to justify this position by pointing to the massive amount of personal data collected daily in all spheres of society, arguing that genomics will do little to change this situation. On the side of Can.Heal professionals, some fear that excessive attention to genomic data would lead to various degrees of protection among different types of personal data, which could result in a lower degree of privacy protection for non-genomic data.

The Power of Genomic Data

Wherever they situate themselves on this continuum, citizens, patients, and Can.Heal professionals acknowledge the power of genomic data, and all the more so in the context of massive reuse at the European level, as pursued in several European projects, such as the Can.Heal platform¹², the BIMG initiative¹³, and the European Health Data Space¹⁴. In the view of lay and professional stakeholders, the power of genomic data can be explained in several ways, which are interconnected.

First, genomic data includes unique individual-level information. However, according to professionals, this topic is more complex, ranging from small-panel tumor testing to whole-genome sequencing with or without linked medical data. The issue of data subjects' identification depends on the amount and type of data collected, but there is overall agreement that there are many circumstances where genomic data can never be considered fully anonymized.

¹² Can.Heal (n.d.).

¹³ BIMG (n.d.). Beyond 1 Million Genomes. Available at: <https://b1mg-project.eu/> (accessed 13 November 2024).

¹⁴ EHDS (n.d.). The European Health Data Space. Available at: <https://www.european-health-data-space.com/> (accessed 13 November 2024).

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Second, genomic data are a goldmine for many actors pursuing different goals in various contexts. There is always a latent risk that some actors re-identify individuals through their data for undesired and unforeseen purposes (e.g. discrimination of people with a higher risk of developing a rare or incurable disease in the health insurance context). In other words, fully anticipating and controlling data reuse is hardly achievable. The uncertainty about potential misuse creates anxiety, unease, and a sense of vulnerability among citizens. While they expect to help people and benefit directly or indirectly from data reuse, they realize they expose themselves and their relatives to vulnerabilities too, such as discrimination, stigmatization, or the loss of privacy. That applies to all members of society but is specifically relevant for already vulnerable groups, such as rare disease patients or ethnic minorities. Genomic data reuse should avoid reinforcing existing inequalities that already constitute barriers for some groups to access genomic medicine and participate in research projects.

Third, genomic data are powerful because of their potential to generate numerous health benefits at the individual and societal levels. Therefore, citizens and patients insist that only trustworthy actors (re)use their data for purposes that align with their values, such as improving individual and public health through personalized medicine in prevention, diagnosis, and treatment. In addition, many patients and citizens draw attention to the power of genomic medicine to reinforce or reduce healthcare inequalities. Data reuse must benefit all citizens, with particular attention to vulnerable groups. The latter are underrepresented in genomic population samples, meaning that some research might be biased and result in genomic technologies that are less relevant for those populations. Researchers, public health actors, and clinicians must ensure that personalized medicine is not the privilege of the few but offers better chances of a healthy life for everyone. In other words, the personalization of medicine should not lead to an individualistic conception of care but, on the contrary, to a more inclusive society.

Genomic Data As (Almost) Always Linked to Individuals

In line with the power they associate with genomic data, patients, citizens, and Can.Heal professionals share another fundamental common ground, which frames their conception of privacy in genomics and, more broadly, the ethics of data reuse. Generally speaking, they tend to recognize that, even under privacy measures, genomic data always remain linked to individuals, especially in the context of massive reuse.

Many patients and citizens continue to regard genomic data, even when de-identified as much as possible, as an intimate part of themselves that they are ready to share for the good of society. Data sharing is regularly described as a mutually beneficial agreement, either as solidarity (the more data are shared, the more valuable they are) or reciprocity (obtaining direct or indirect benefits). As a

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consequence, the link between the data and the person behind it never disappears, and privacy protection should not be interpreted as erasing the link to the data subject. On the contrary, since data subjects share sensitive data to help others and put their trust in data users to generate societal benefits, they expect their values to be respected, or at least taken into account, in the governance of genomic data. Some lay people consider that data users enter into a relationship with data subjects whenever they reuse genomic information. This relationship can take various forms, which will be explored in the next section (*Reuse of Genomic Data for Clinical Purposes*). In addition, patients and citizens understand that personalized medicine, which they highly support, requires (re)identifiable data and efficient data flows between various health-related professionals, such as clinicians and researchers. As a result, they pinpoint the need for proportionality between potential privacy risks and the benefits of massively reusing genomic information in the clinical, research, and public health contexts. For example, some patients and citizens support pseudonymization techniques with entrusted data users and for purposes and contexts in which anonymization would render individual and societal benefits unachievable. Yet, outside the research and clinical contexts, patients and citizens favor more robust security measures (e.g. anonymization) to avoid anyone turning their data against them.

On their side, Can.Heal professionals acknowledge the risk but also the need to be able to re-identify data subjects to achieve the promises of personalized medicine. As the value of genomic datasets increases through accurate and updated linkage with phenotypes, so too does the sensitivity of datasets¹⁵. More specifically, they insist on the need to create better interactions between the research and the clinical contexts, whose objectives are often complementary. Clinicians might need to be informed by researchers about study results that could improve the decision-making process for their patients in a more personalized way, and researchers might need specific information about diseases they cannot access because of privacy measures. A case in point is the Deciphering Developmental Disorders (DDD) project where clinicians and researchers actively collaborated for the benefit of young rare disease patients. Initially, they were able to report diagnosis to 27% of the 1,133 participating children and their families (whole-exome sequencing) and, three years later, increased their diagnosis rate to 40% thanks to progress in scientific knowledge on developmental disorder-associated genes¹⁶. However, most often, there is a lack of interoperability between research and clinical procedures (e.g. consent form, type of data processed) that Can.Heal professionals identify as a barrier to overcome. For instance, clinicians deal with identifiable data to treat patients appropriately and in due time. In contrast, researchers usually process de-identified data since going

¹⁵ Horton and Lucassen (2023).

¹⁶ Wright CF et al. (2018). Making new genetic diagnoses with old data: Iterative reanalysis and reporting from genome-wide data in 1,133 families with developmental disorders. *Genetics in Medicine* 20 (10): 1216-1223.

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back to patients is unnecessary, provided they can access sufficient clinical data to carry out their projects. Can.Heal professionals argue that increased information exchanges, for example, by sharing the codes of pseudonymized data, could lead to improvement in both care and research. Nevertheless, they also refer to the potential risks of this crossover between clinics and research, in particular human errors, such as accidental data leakage or confusion in patients' profiles. When sharing codes of pseudonymized data, professionals could mistakenly mix up patients and thereby generate misguided treatment options, which runs counter to personalized medicine. Technical solutions and secure digital systems should help avoid these human errors in genomic data reuse, particularly when multiple medical institutions and research centers are involved.

What Privacy Is About in Genomic Data Reuse

One of the reasons why lay people care so much about their privacy lies in their fear of losing control of information, the disclosure of which would negatively change how others see and treat them as members of the broader society. That is all the more important since people could be stigmatized or discriminated against based on genetic components they have no control over. Patients, citizens, and Can.Heal professionals all emphasize the importance of protective and preventive measures that complement privacy security measures, such as laws against discrimination/stigmatization and sanctions in case of abuse. According to patients and citizens, privacy protection goes beyond withholding people's identity because it aims to preserve other individual rights, such as the liberty of actions, the right to an open future ('not being prisoners of their genome'), and social and psychological well-being by avoiding inequalities. Among the many possible inequalities, patients and citizens insist on the exclusion of disabled people, the differentiation between 'healthy and unhealthy' DNA, the risk of a standardized genome as the imposed norm while every genome is unique, and eugenics (designer babies, genetic selection that significantly reduces human diversity).

By sharing genomic data, patients and citizens realize they also give more power to actors who can render them vulnerable intentionally or unintentionally, generating power imbalances if adequate safeguards are not implemented. Power imbalances can happen in every sector, including healthcare, but lay people distrust for-profit actors the most, such as employers, banks, insurance, and pharmaceutical companies. When data users primarily pursue profit-making purposes, citizens feel used as a means to achieving external interests, which is incompatible with their values oriented towards the common good. What lay people mean by the common good varies across public engagement initiatives. Generally speaking, it encompasses healthcare improvement at the individual and population levels to build a fair society where everyone has an equal chance to live healthily,

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including more vulnerable and disadvantaged groups. Healthcare professionals and researchers are usually the most trusted actors because they are expected to (re)use data for medicine and scientific progress, which are supposed to contribute to the common good.

Discussion on Ethical Implications and Resulting Recommendations

Privacy in genomics is a particularly complex topic because it raises ethical, legal, and scientific aspects that relate to each other but do not automatically coincide. From a scientific perspective, the sensitivity of genomic data mainly depends on three factors influencing the degree of identifiability of data subjects: (1) the nature of the data determining its uniqueness (rare versus common variant), (2) the amount of data processed (whole-genome or exome sequencing versus repeated genotypes in large populations; genomic data combined with other personal data, such as demographic) and (3) the amount of phenotypic data linked to the genomic data¹⁷. From a legal perspective, Article 4(1) of the GDPR recognizes genomic data as personal if they relate to an identified or identifiable natural person¹⁸, considering all methods that might be used to re-identify data subjects and the degree of reasonability of these methods (cost, time, and accessibility of the technology)¹⁹. Moreover, genomic data also fall under the category of sensitive data in the GDPR because their processing may threaten some fundamental rights and freedoms of data subjects, such as exposing them to discrimination²⁰. The legal aspects of genomic data reuse within Can.Heal are covered by WP12.1 Deliverable. From an ethical and stakeholder involvement perspective, the sensitivity of genomic data is determined by several factors, including the ethical status attributed to genomic data (exceptionalism or not), the values, needs, and concerns associated with it, and how different stakeholders balance the risk and the benefit ratio in genomic data reuse.

Hence, if onco-genomic professionals only rely on scientific and legal guidelines to protect the privacy of data subjects but ignore the ethical aspects and what matters to citizens and patients (i.e. their values, needs, and concerns), they might unintentionally damage public trust by reusing genomic data in misalignment with what lay people consider ethical conduct. The perception of ethical conduct is not universal²¹. Yet, several studies demonstrated that the ethical behavior of data users greatly

¹⁷ Rahnasto J (2023). Genetic data are not always personal: Disaggregating the identifiability and sensitivity of genetic data. *Journal of Law and the Biosciences* 10 (2): Isad029.

¹⁸ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation) [2016] OJ L 119/1.

¹⁹ DPO Europe GmbH (2018-2014). Recital 26. Available at: <https://gdpr-text.com/read/recital-26/> (accessed 6 November 2024).

²⁰ Rahnasto (2023).

²¹ Horton and Lucassen (2023).

influences people’s willingness to contribute to data sharing²²⁻²³. Therefore, it is critical to verify whether there is misalignment or alignment between what professionals (data users) and lay people (data subjects) perceive as ethical conduct in genomic data reuse.

Our results show that lay and expert stakeholders have complementary visions of trustworthiness in privacy protection due to divergent points of attention, but they still align because of shared ambitions and values. Their main divergence relates to the ethical status they assign to genomic data—exceptional versus non-exceptional—that, in turn, influences their approach to privacy (individual-focused versus misuse-focused) and what they judge ethically acceptable or not in data reuse. It has been demonstrated in a Belgian citizen forum that how participants viewed the human genome greatly influenced which genomic data usage they deemed ethical and trustworthy and under which conditions²⁴.

It must be noted that the individual-focused approach assigned to the general public and the misuse-focused approach attributed to professionals are merely general trends observed in our results. There is no consensus in either group since some experts defend an exceptionalist approach to genomics whereas some lay people adhere to a non-exceptionalist approach.

Individual-Focused Approach

Whatever privacy protection measures are applied, the majority of lay people consider genomic data as sensitive and personal by nature for two leading reasons.

The first reason is the ever-latent and expanding risk of re-identification, over which data subjects have no control, even though they have to bear the consequences in their own lives. The more data there is, the greater the risk of re-identification. Accordingly, computational tools have proven their ability to re-identify individuals in aggregated datasets because of the small number of identifiers required to trace an individual²⁵. Although data degradation methods exist to limit re-identification (e.g. to snip large DNA regions into small pieces), these methods often reduce the value of the data for clinical and research purposes. What is more, statistical correlations between genotypes at various genomic loci may lead to the recombination of the small DNA pieces and, hence, to the re-identification of data subjects²⁶. Outside health-related contexts, criminal investigations have used

²² European Commission (2021). European citizens’ knowledge and attitudes towards science and technology. Report Special Eurobarometer 516, European Commission, April-May.

²³ Critchley C, Nicol D, and McWhirter R (2017). Identifying public expectations of genetic biobanks. *Public understanding of science* 26 (6): 671-687.

²⁴ Mayeur C and Van Hoof W (2021). Citizens' conceptions of the genome: Related values and practical implications in a citizen forum on the use of genomic information. *Health Expectations* 00:1-10.

²⁵ Rahnasto (2023).

²⁶ Rahnasto (2023).

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family-matching techniques in direct-to-consumer genealogy databases to solve serial killer cases that had been put on hold for decades²⁷. By cross-referring de-identified genomic data with genealogy databases, the police can trace the identity of numerous individuals and their relatives²⁸. Although the objective pursued by those techniques is laudable, individuals are usually not informed of the reuse of their genetic data for such purpose, which is highly problematic given that genealogy databases include the data of tens of millions of people across the world²⁹. A study using relatedness testing models has demonstrated that about 60% of individuals with European ancestry could be re-identified through genetic information available in genealogy databases, despite a great number having never done any genealogy testing³⁰.

Additionally, technological and scientific advances create further uncertainties regarding the potential to re-identify people in future data reuse. As research is increasingly oriented toward genome-wide studies and big data, it becomes highly complex to foresee and control the possibility of re-identification and its consequences for data subjects. Since all genomic sequences will likely be attributed extra significance in the future, they might become sensitive in some contexts where they are now considered harmless³¹. The covid pandemic is a case in point. This unpredictable international health crisis gave medical meaning to genomic variants related to a higher susceptibility to SARS-CoV-2³². In less democratic systems, such knowledge could be used as preventive health policy by applying stricter rules to people with greater susceptibility to COVID-19, such as reducing their right to free movement and related privacy rights, even though they are not contaminated yet. The literature review on public engagement initiatives highlights the fear of health dictatorship and control of individuals through their genomic data as a lesson learned from the pandemic, especially in the current unstable political landscapes in Europe and worldwide.

The second leading reason why many lay people consider genomic data as nearly always personal is that their reuse will impact their life at an intimate level positively or negatively (e.g. preventive measures changing lifestyle versus receiving unexpected and uncertain results with family implications). Consequently, data users must never forget that a human being is behind genomic data and has specific values, concerns, and needs, as well as preferences in what their lives should be (e.g. carefree attitude by dealing with problems as they arise versus a more controlled and preventive

²⁷ Mayeur C and Van Hoof W (2023). L'utilisation ultérieure des données génétiques dans un contexte criminalistique : Enjeux éthiques et perspectives citoyennes. *Droit & Santé - Revue luxembourgeoise*: 9-16.

²⁸ Horton and Lucassen (2023).

²⁹ Mayeur and Van Hoof (2023).

³⁰ Erlich Y, Shor T, Pe'er I, et al. (2018). Identity inference of genomic data using long-range familial searches. *Science* 362 (6415): 690-694.

³¹ Rahnasto (2023).

³² Horton and Lucassen (2023).

approach to life and its many risks). Those ethical components behind the data deserve respect in the name of the autonomy of people contributing to data sharing for the benefit of society. Recommendations on the practical means by which data users could respect lay values, needs, concerns, and preferences are thoroughly described in the final report of the TEHDAS initiative (Toward the European Health Data Space)³³ and are further explored in the present deliverable in the section *Reuse of Genomic Data for Clinical Purposes*. Some legal scholars have held a similar position by recognizing the uniquely intimate and personal nature of genomic data and stating that they deserve greater protection than other types of sensitive data because their processing will have direct implications on individual autonomy, which must be safeguarded as a fundamental right³⁴⁻³⁵⁻³⁶. Generally speaking, privacy regulations have assumed that individuals have no interest in how their data are reused as long as they are anonymous and processed lawfully³⁷. Because anonymizing genomic data becomes more and more elusive, one could conclude that individuals nearly always have an interest in the reuse of their genomic data. In other words, depersonalizing the data from a technical and legal perspective should not equal depersonalizing them from an ethical perspective.

Hence, privacy can be defined as individuals' right to protect and control, as far as feasible, the dissemination of intimate information to the external world because of the impact this dissemination can have on how individuals are perceived and treated³⁸⁻³⁹. That is especially important since negative consequences might extend to relatives, and genomic information does not fundamentally change over time, making the potential for discrimination even more persistent⁴⁰⁻⁴¹. Yet, in the context of massive genomic data reuse, a realistic conception of privacy must also encompass the impossibility of controlling every dissemination of intimate information because of the unavoidable risk of re-identification and its parallel need to achieve the promise of personalized medicine⁴²⁻⁴³. Many patients and citizens are ready to embrace that new conception of privacy on the condition that data reuse

³³ TEHDAS (2023). Qualitative study to assess citizens' perception of sharing health data for secondary use and recommendations on how to engage citizens in the EHDS. Report.

³⁴ Bonython W and Arnold BB (2015). Privacy, personhood, and property in the age of genomics. *Laws* 4 (3) :377-412.

³⁵ Hallinan D, Friedewald M, and De Hert P (2013). Genetic data and the data protection regulation: Anonymity, multiple subjects, sensitivity and a prohibitory logic regarding genetic data? *Computer Law & Security Review* 29: 317-329.

³⁶ European Court of Human Rights (2008). Case of S. and Marper V. The United Kingdom, Applications n° 30,562/04 and 30,566/04. Strasbourg. Available at: <https://hudoc.echr.coe.int/fre?i=001-90051> (accessed 14 November 2024).

³⁷ Rahnasto (2023).

³⁸ Rahnasto (2023).

³⁹ Mayeur C, Mertes H, and Van Hoof W (2023).

⁴⁰ Rahnasto (2023).

⁴¹ Horton and Lucassen (2023).

⁴² Mayeur C, Mertes H, and Van Hoof W (2023).

⁴³ Haeusermann T, Fadda M, Blasimme A, et al. (2018). Genes wide open: Data sharing and the social gradient of genomic privacy. *AJOB Empirical Bioethics* 9 (4): 207-221.

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remains ethical in the sense of reliable (as secured as possible), trustworthy (alignment between reuse purposes and lay values), and accountable (protection against misuse and sanctions in case of abuse).

Misuse-Focused Approach

In contrast with the exceptional approach to genomics of most citizens and patients, Can.Heal professionals fear that exceptionalism would lead to various degrees of protection among different types of personal data, resulting in lower privacy protection for non-genomic data. This stance against genetic exceptionalism and the following equally high standards of confidentiality for all medical data have been supported previously by European expert groups⁴⁴. Some have argued that granting particular protection to all genetic data is irrelevant because numerous genetic sequences are not individual-specific (common in some populations or even universally shared) or have too little personal significance (e.g. molecular markers with no health implications or variants whose function is still unknown). Moreover, when some genetic data are categorized as sensitive, they are usually no more sensitive than other personal data reused massively in big data (e.g. location or social media data).⁴⁵ Therefore, some scholars defend a more careful and context-specific approach to genetic data by assessing their practical sensitivity instead of putting all of them under the same category of sensitive and personal data⁴⁶. Nevertheless, many professionals and scholars still recognize that genomic data are somehow exceptional to a certain degree due to their enduring and intimate link with individuals⁴⁷.

Instead of focusing on the controversy of whether genomic data are exceptional or not, Can.Heal professionals mainly approach the problem of privacy by focusing on the risk of data misuse, which constitutes a zone of agreement among lay and professional stakeholders. Privacy cannot be reflected upon on its own but must be placed in the broader context of social realities (stigma, discrimination, inequalities) that shape the actual rights enjoyed by different people. For example, people with a particularly high risk of incurable disease could be discriminated against by health insurance companies in the same way as people diagnosed with the disease. Several studies have shown that genetic determinism is a belief that is more widespread than it should be, including in the media and schools⁴⁸⁻⁴⁹. Consequently, although genetic determinism is inaccurate from a scientific point of view,

⁴⁴ Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (2004). 25 recommendations on the ethical, legal and social implications of genetic testing. Report, European Commission, Belgium.

⁴⁵ Rahnasto (2023).

⁴⁶ Rahnasto (2023).

⁴⁷ Rahnasto (2023).

⁴⁸ Mayeur C, Mertes H, and Van Hoof W (2023). Do genomic passports leave us more vulnerable or less vulnerable? Perspectives from an online citizen engagement. *Humanities & Social Sciences Communications* 10: 83.

⁴⁹ Carver R, Castéra J, Gericke N, et al. (2017). Young adults' belief in genetic determinism, and knowledge and attitudes towards modern genetics and genomics: The PUGGS questionnaire. *PLoS One* 12 (1): e0169808.

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some actors (e.g. health insurance or employers) might still discriminate against people with a high risk of incurable disease, even if they never contract the disease, because health insurances do not want to take that risk. That is why privacy cannot ignore the social realities in which it is rooted⁵⁰.

The influence of social realities on privacy protection is all the more important for groups who are already particularly vulnerable, either due to socio-historical reasons (ethnic minorities), (epi)genetic causes (rare disease patients), or socio-economic disadvantages. Those groups deserve special considerations and protection in any health policy decision making and data governance strategies in order to avoid reinforcing existing inequalities. For instance, it is critical to improve the representativity of ethnic minorities in genomic population samples to avoid biases in research results and following less relevant clinical care for those populations. The Genome of Europe initiative, which has recently been launched, will cover those specific aspects at the EU level⁵¹. Researchers, public health actors, and clinicians have a moral responsibility to ensure that personalized medicine benefits all citizens and in particular vulnerable groups, which requires extra efforts to involve them because of their general mistrust toward healthcare professionals and any authorities. Accordingly, their voice should be more represented in public engagement initiatives on ethical issues in genomics to study the additional challenges they face in order to improve their situation.

Although the risk of data misuse exists everywhere, Can.Heal professionals argue that the trustworthiness of data users in the clinical and research contexts—i.e. the alignment with the lay values and aspirations related to personalized medicine—should guarantee the benefit-risk ratio is acceptable in reusing pseudonymized data to enable effective dynamics between oncological research and clinical care. Furthermore, some Can.Heal professionals point out that, when reusing genomic data in their daily practice, researchers are not primarily interested in the individual behind it but more in the individual characteristics of the data needed to conduct their research project and directly or indirectly improve medical care at a global level. In that sense, one could claim that research projects with no direct clinical implications on patients respect the privacy of individuals, and treat the data as if they were “depersonalized” although not totally de-identified. The main problem lies in the risk of involuntary privacy breach when sharing pseudonymized codes among hospitals or research units, which could be partially solved through improved secured digital systems.

⁵⁰ Rahnasto (2023).

⁵¹ Beyond One Million Genomes (n.d.). The Genome of Europe (GoE): Realising a population genomic reference cohort of at least 500,000 citizens across Europe by 2022. Report, European Commission, Belgium.

Recommendations Combining Lay and Expert Approaches to Privacy

Privacy and Trustworthiness in Genomic Data Reuse

Some scholars defend that the trustworthiness of genomic data reuse practices partially depends on how honest professionals are toward citizens and patients regarding realistic privacy protection and its limitations⁵². The first step toward this would be to explain when and why genomic data can be considered anonymous and to what extent, and not try to dissimulate when the risk of re-identification is too high. In this regard, Horton and Lucassen (2023) made practical suggestions of formulations: “rather than saying ‘your data will be kept anonymous’ and caveating this separately, maybe we should say ‘your data will be kept as anonymous as we can make them’. Rather than saying ‘your data stay in the data centre’ we should say ‘we work hard to ensure that your data stay in the data centre’.”⁵³ Informing people in a transparent and honest manner is one of the conditions for being trustworthy because it offers them the opportunity to act accordingly and avoids disillusionment in case of data misuse, which would damage their trust in data users even more than if they had been aware of the risk⁵⁴.

Recommendation 1 - *Data users must be honest and realistic towards lay people regarding the privacy protection of their genomic data in order to remain trustworthy, including the practical risk of re-identification and under which conditions.*

Privacy Should Be Context-Dependent

The risk of re-identifying data subjects and the consequences on their life is continuously evolving depending on several factors, such as the type of data reused and the intention behind the reuse⁵⁵. Consequently, the appropriate level of privacy protection must be dynamic and context-specific, with particular attention to the purpose of reuse that must be in line with the lay values. For instance, pseudonymization is considered acceptable to improve the dynamics between the clinical and research contexts because lay people support personalized medicine. Outside of these contexts, more robust security measures should be favored to avoid data misuse (e.g. discrimination or stigmatization), but also because the for-profit sector that could reuse genomic data (bank, employment, insurance) is not in line with the lay values. The pharmaceutical industry remains a gray zone because they are needed for drug and treatment development (pharmacogenomics) but, many times, they pursued private gains as their main objective. There should be contractual agreements

⁵² Horton and Lucassen (2023).

⁵³ Horton and Lucassen (2023), p. 47.

⁵⁴ Bilodeau, Cumyn, Ménard, et al. (2024).

⁵⁵ Rahnasto (2023).

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between public health authorities and the pharmaceutical industry to better regulate and control this sector in a way that serves society first, or at least equally to private gains, especially when public funds are injected.

The proportionality and dynamics in privacy protection measures in view of the context and intention of data users is a growing trend in the literature⁵⁶. Instead of labeling all genomic data under the rigid category of sensitive data, controllers should assess the concrete risk for re-identification in light of the other data available and technologies used in the specific context. Such active surveillance could only be applied to data presenting a common high risk of re-identification to avoid legal overburdening⁵⁷. Indeed, there is a general problem of strict regulations and unharmonized interpretation of rules among the various contexts in which genomic data are reused whereas there must be collaboration between those contexts to reach the promises of personalized medicine. Hence, an increasing number of scholars claim the need for a more flexible and principle-based approach to privacy instead of strict legal rules⁵⁸. Both Can.Heal professionals and the general public request a more flexible legal framework that is supportive of genomic data sharing but that also acknowledges the risks behind it in a realistic manner. The notion of risks is highly complex in genomic data reuse and impossible to tackle if the goal is to create a risk-averse society. Most lay and expert stakeholders would agree to take more reasonable risks, for instance, regarding the re-identification of data subjects, if reliable security structures are implemented and that data users remain trustworthy, as extensively developed in this report. Finally, given that genomic data reuse crosses the borders of Member States, it becomes urgent to harmonize anti-discrimination and anti-stigmatization laws at the European level.

Recommendation 2 - *Privacy protection measures should be dynamic and context-dependent by assessing the practical risk of re-identification to enable more flexible and effective data reuse in various contexts for the benefit of patients and citizens. Yet, it also implies EU harmonized laws against discrimination and stigmatization at the European level to ensure equality in the protection of data subjects across Member States.*

Involvement of Data Subjects Should Be Context-Dependent

Many patients and citizens want to be empowered in the protection of their privacy through various forms of involvement in data governance. The opportunity to play a more active role could alleviate the frustration of some at being paternalistically subjected to the reuse of data and its impact on their

⁵⁶ Wright CF, Hurlles ME, and Firth HV (2016). Principle of proportionality in genomic data sharing. *Nature Reviews Genetics* 17 (1): 1-2.

⁵⁷ Rahnasto (2023).

⁵⁸ Horton and Lucassen (2023).

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lives without having any say in the matter. Some scholars have argued that providing a certain level of control to individuals over the processing of their genomic data has significance from a human rights perspective, given the implications of such processing on their privacy⁵⁹. Yet, the involvement of data subjects should be context-dependent to ensure that data reuse remains efficient. Respecting each individual value and preference is unrealistic and even not desirable in contexts where data reuse does not directly impact the lives of individuals, such as fundamental research and public health policies because the link with data subjects is secondary⁶⁰. Notwithstanding, the core and shared values of patients and citizens as a community (e.g. solidarity, reciprocity, autonomy, protection of vulnerable groups, equity in access to healthcare) should always be respected.

Recommendation 3 - *The degree of involvement of lay people in data governance should be context-dependent and dynamic. The higher the risk of re-identification, the more lay people want to be involved because the greater the consequences will be on their lives. For instance, in the public health context, mere information about the fact that data is reused might be enough. In the research context, lay people expect more in terms of transparency, traceability, and opt-out consent. In the clinical context, informed consent and genetic counseling are key to empowering data subjects. The various levels of data subjects' involvement are explained in the section Reuse of Genomic Data for Clinical Purposes.*

⁵⁹ Hallinan, Friedewald, and De Hert (2013).

⁶⁰ Rahnasto (2023).

Reuse of Genomic Data for Clinical Purposes

Introduction

In the clinical context, genomic sequencing data can be used far beyond the specific case in which these data have initially been generated, sequenced, and analyzed. This way, many people could benefit from genomic data sharing and reuse in diagnostic and treatment settings⁶¹. This type of genomic data reuse includes practices such as improving patient records, comparing cases, building databases, informing clinical interpretations, and developing or improving clinical decision support tools⁶². In other words, genomic data reuse for clinical purposes exploits the opportunities of clinical data beyond their relevance for the index person to further support and improve the clinical care of all (future) patients, from relatives to unrelated persons with a similar genetic make-up. Practices like these contribute to a learning healthcare system in which the value of existing genomic data is fully exploited to support and improve the clinical care of all⁶³.

Genomic Data as Individual and Collective Entity

The benefits of reusing genomic data for clinical purposes can only be realized when the data of numerous patients are collectively and systematically accessible for reuse. However, the personal and sensitive nature of genomic data still underpins individual, autonomous choices and decision-making regarding these data. Hence, in the context of genomic data reuse for clinical purposes, the duality of genomic data as both an individual and a collective entity is emphasized, revealing a tension between respect for (individual) autonomy and support for the common good.

⁶¹ Evans BJ and Jarvik GP (2018). Impact of HIPAA's minimum necessary standard on genomic data sharing. *Genetics in Medicine* 20(5): 531-535.

⁶² Meystre SM, Lovis C, Bürkle T, et al. (2017). Clinical data reuse or secondary use: Current status and potential future progress. *Yearbook of Medical Informatics* 26: 38-52.

⁶³ Evans and Jarvik (2018).

FIGURE 4 - Genomic data as individual and collective entity

Genomic Data as Individual & Collective Entity

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Patients and citizens frequently refer to the dual nature of genomic data as both an individual and collective entity, as well as to the tension between autonomy and the common good. On the one hand, they interpret the value of autonomy as the right to be respected in their preferences and choices on whether their genomic data should be included in data reuse initiatives. A major determinant in this consideration is whether or not the purpose of reuse aligns with their values. On the other hand, patients and citizens consider genomic data as a collective entity and they reflect on the benefits that could be realized if genomic data were reused to understand, prevent, diagnose, or treat similar cases of disease. This collective dimension of genomics might create a responsibility towards relatives and other patients in general to support data reuse for clinical purposes. This responsibility is further endorsed by citizen-supported values, such as solidarity and altruism. In the context of genomic data reuse, solidarity refers to the fact that the more data are shared, the more insightful their analysis becomes both for the data subject and other patients. Altruism, on its side, relates to the idea that genomic data reuse constitutes an indirect way of helping others, for instance, through research. This idea of collective usefulness, whether in the form of solidarity or altruism, might stimulate people to contribute to increased data flows and health data reuse to improve healthcare for all.

The duality of genomic data as both an individual and a collective entity again raises the question of who should decide on reuse. On the one hand, many patients and citizens want to have an oversight of how their genomic data are being reused, as well as (in varying degrees and in different ways) the possibility of being involved in this reuse. They want, for example, to be able to opt out of data reuse or withdraw their data, especially if there is no alignment between the purpose of reuse and their own values. This option should also be available if the purpose of reuse changes over time. On the other hand, patients and citizens acknowledge professionals' duty of care in a clinical context, as well as their responsibility to protect and treat patients the best way possible. They are aware that professionals need the data of others to adequately interpret their patients' data and be able to report significant results that could prevent disease, refine a diagnosis, or optimize treatments. Therefore, professional duties should be balanced with people's rights and autonomous choices, including the preference of opting out of data reuse. One suggestion to moderate this tension between individual rights and professional duties regards the practice of shared decision-making. Professionals should explain the possibilities, risks and practical applications of genomic data reuse, while patients/citizens should be allowed to share their concerns, ask their questions and have their values respected. This way, mutual trust and understanding can be established that allow for a joint deliberation. Consequently, decisions on genomic data reuse can become a shared responsibility between patients, citizens, and professionals and effective, value-supported decisions on reuse can be made.

Consent Procedures and the Impact of Established Regulations

FIGURE 5 - Consent regulations regarding the reuse of genomic data

In the balancing act that includes the interests of various stakeholders (including patients, citizens, researchers, and healthcare professionals), Can.Heal professionals indicated the need to also consider

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the impact of established regulations. In the context of genomic data reuse for clinical purposes, important regulations that are specifically relevant are those regarding informed consent since they are one of the most widespread practical translations of the value of respect for patients' autonomy.

Overall, patients, citizens, and Can.Heal professionals acknowledge informed consent as a potentially valuable tool to respect autonomy and personal preferences. However, consent regulations and practices may also be challenging under certain circumstances. In this regard, lay people and experts put different emphases.

Can.Heal Professionals

Can.Heal professionals extensively question the contexts in which consent procedures might be a feasible and valuable approach. Currently, different consent procedures are applied in different contexts because of the different types of data that are processed. In a research context, mainly de-identified data are processed since going back to patients is unnecessary, provided that researchers can access sufficient clinical data to carry out their projects. Conversely, clinicians mostly deal with identifiable data to treat patients appropriately and in due time (see section *Genomic Data As (Almost) Always Linked to Individuals*). The consent procedures in both contexts may be very different and largely incompatible, also regarding the reuse of genomic data, yet for a more streamlined reuse of genomic data for clinical purposes, increased and more efficient interactions between researchers and clinicians might be required, as well as more compatible consent procedures.

In the research context, informed consent procedures are often required and some Can.Heal professionals seem to consider this requirement as rather problematic. First, a need for opt-in consent may discourage researchers and hamper the recruitment of study participants. They illustrate this by referring to the Belgian BeSolveRD study, in which all Belgian genetic centers participate but where the requirement and practical burden of obtaining consent seems to disincentive researchers in active recruitment. Second, Can.Heal professionals warn that explicit consent procedures may result in a high rate of data withdrawal among patients, which would impede research and undermine study objectives. Third, they indicate that consent procedures sometimes differ per research center or even per research unit, which constitutes an additional barrier for effective collaboration in genomic data reuse among researchers, as well as between researchers and clinicians.

Despite the potential downsides of informed consent procedures, several Can.Heal professionals refer to evidence that when opt-out possibilities are offered for genomic data reuse (e.g. for research), very few people actually choose to opt out. Instead, patients and citizens seem to be willing to contribute to data reuse that could help others (e.g. shorten the waiting time in diagnosis) because that purpose of reuse aligns with their values (e.g. solidarity, altruism). This way, Can.Heal professionals

claim that there seems to be no reason not to allow opt-out possibilities. In this regard, some recall that routine clinical data might be reused without consent when there is compliance with the legal basis concerning public interest. Data subjects are then informed about their data being reused but they do not have the possibility to opt out. However, this procedure in which people cannot refuse the further processing of their genomic data also generates ethical discussions. Some Can.Heal professionals point out the difference between legal requirements and ethical practice: even though consent might not always be legally required, it might be good ethical practice to nevertheless provide it. By providing the choice to opt out, fundamental rights, such as respect for autonomy and self-determination, could be respected without undermining research objectives and, more generally, without compromising reuse opportunities. Professionals compared this approach with, for example, Austria's law on organ donation. It provides organ donation as the default option at the time of death, unless individuals explicitly opt out. This approach successfully leads to a high number of organ donations when compared to other countries where opt-in requirements are in place. Such a requirement might leave many people unaware that they explicitly have to opt in, even when they might have been disposed to donate. Professionals suggest a similar pattern regarding the reuse of genomic data, where opt-in approaches might create considerable barriers towards the potential benefits of reuse. Consequently, Can.Heal professionals argue that if consent would be a requirement for the reuse of genomic data for clinical purposes, opt-out procedures would be preferable over opt-in procedures. Practically speaking, opt-out procedures could take the form of consent withdrawal or objection to data processing, depending on the GDPR legal basis. Nevertheless, to ensure that genomic data reuse for clinical purposes is boosted within this possibility of opt-out procedures, Can.Heal professionals consider it essential to establish a societal culture supportive of data reuse in the clinical and research contexts.

Patients and Citizens

Patients and citizens consider informed consent procedures to be an agreement between professionals and individuals that goes beyond legal obligations. Consent materializes the relationship between data users and data subjects (see section *Genomic Data As (Almost) Always Linked to Individuals*) and the way they both sign up for specific conditions, benefits, and risks. However, many patients and citizens also agree that consent procedures should not hamper research. In particular, they refer to problematic cases where research participants request for data withdrawal while consent has previously been given.

To reconcile both ideas, patients and citizens consider the most suitable ways of giving consent. Since many lay people acknowledge the importance of research, many would accept automatic

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genomic data reuse for clinical purposes, for instance through research projects, but with an option to opt out. This shows that in some contexts, nudging is considered acceptable since this will allow for a large-scale data reuse supporting societal benefits. However, genomic data reuse by default should comply with several conditions, such as robust and reliable data protection, transparency, alignment between reuse purposes and personal values, and the maintenance of opt-out possibilities. Given that purposes such as progress in healthcare, personalized medicine, and scientific research align with the values of many patients and citizens, opt-out rates should not reach a level to which it significantly hampers reuse activities. Additionally, dynamic consent procedures that allow for adjusted choices over time (for instance, in case of changed purposes of reuse) and for sustainable ways of active involvement in data governance are often mentioned as a favorable procedure, especially in a context of reuse for research purposes.

Understanding Genomic Data Reuse

Patients, citizens, and Can.Heal professionals all underline the importance of realizing a better understanding of genomics and genomic data reuse, both at the individual and at the societal level. From an individual angle, informing data subjects about the meaning, potential benefits, and impact of genomic data reuse will contribute to the ability of making informed decisions regarding their own health management and health data governance. From a societal angle, Can.Heal professionals and lay people believe that raising societal awareness and increasing genetic literacy regarding the value of genomic data reuse is central to the establishment of a societal culture supportive of genomics and data reuse.

FIGURE 6 - Understanding genomic data reuse

Informing Data Subjects

In general, many patients and citizens want to be informed about genomic data reuse. Receiving the right type and amount of information is the prerequisite for their involvement in data governance

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and, as a result, to improve trust and empowerment in genomics and data reuse (see the Discussion on Ethical Implication in Privacy). Yet, to be useful for lay people, the information provided should meet certain conditions, including being transparent and traceable, as well as accessible and personalized.

Transparency and Traceability

Patients and citizens emphasize how information about genomic data reuse should be transparent and this by clearly indicating who reuses their data for which purposes. In line with the idea of many lay people that the reuse of genomic data equals the establishment of a relationship between data users and data subjects, patients and citizens think that transparent communication should not be a one-time activity (e.g. broad consent with no follow-up) but a continuous engagement, for instance in the form of traceability regarding data reuse, tiered/dynamic consent, or broader public engagement initiatives on the ethical and societal aspects of genomic data. In tiered consent systems a default package of necessary information is presented to all patients or citizens, while more detailed information is provided selectively, depending on specific (and potentially changing) information needs and result preferences. In dynamic consent approaches, patients and citizens are able to give/adjust their consent at several times, for instance prior to genomic testing, prior to the disclosure of results and prior to updates about these results. These types of involvement enable patients and citizens to keep a certain level of oversight and control over what is done with their sensitive health data, which is considered a central requirement for trust and preserving autonomy. Moreover, transparency on data reuse for purposes supported by lay people increases their feeling of contributing to something valuable (see section “What Privacy Is About in Genomic Data Reuse”). While lay people’s preferences regarding the degree of involvement in data governance strongly vary and some people wish to remain passive, this is no reason not to give the opportunity of involvement to the many others who wish to be implicated more actively.

On their side, Can.Heal professionals acknowledge transparency as a cornerstone in genomic data reuse since they witness that it raises the willingness of people to share their data and contribute to research and medical progress. Transparency can take various forms, such as active traceability regarding actual data reuse or consent procedures. In a context of genomic data reuse, consent forms can, for instance, inform patients about the possibility that their clinical data might be reused in research projects that aim to develop support tools for diagnosis or treatment decisions in similar cases of diseases. Nevertheless, Can.Heal professionals also reflect on possibilities to improve transparency beyond consent, for instance through continued follow-up on data reuse that allows patients to check which research projects are reusing their genomic data.

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Patients and citizens suggest implementing centralized and interactive online platforms on which they could trace and follow-up on the reuse of their genomic data, for instance by receiving information or by being offered more active forms of involvement (such as (partial) opt-in/opt-out possibilities). While the feasibility and practical aspects of such platforms still need to be examined, Can.Heal professionals refer to a Belgian model of inspiration hosted by the KU Leuven/UZ Leuven⁶⁴. Through a centralized management system, patients from the reference hospital and associated hospitals can verify in which studies and for which purposes their clinical data are reused. When notified about data reuse in a specific study, patients can contact their physician or the researcher for more information. However, this practice of transparent but automatic reuse of clinical data for research does not include the possibility for people to opt out. Can.Heal professionals compare this practice with routine clinical data reuse for the public interest without consent procedures (as allowed by the GDPR) but with the obligation of informing the data subject. Local initiatives like these could inspire the development of initiatives and infrastructures at national level.

Accessible and Personalized Information

Lay people as well as Can.Heal professionals indicate that information provided to patients and citizens should be communicated in an accessible, comprehensible, more targeted and, ideally, even personalized way, in which professionals try to use layman's language as much as possible. All of them highlight that communication should mainly focus on the personal impact that genomic information might have on people's lives instead of putting too much weight on the technical aspects. Professionals should explain how genomic test results and genomic data reuse can have a psychological impact, as well as a broader impact on one's personal and family life. Moreover, both lay and expert stakeholders mention that professionals should have at their disposal visual tools, such as cartoons or vignettes, to help them vulgarize scientific knowledge to their patients.

Both lay people and professionals refer to the central role that genetic counselors might play in this communication tailored to the personal needs and family context of patients. Yet, to support counselors and more generally healthcare professionals in this communication, it is of utmost importance to adequately train and educate them by offering specific training programs. Also the official recognition of the profession of genetic counselor is considered an important step to be realized in the short term.

Within but also beyond the context of individual medical consultations, both Can.Heal professionals and lay people add that information and communication should be adapted to various

⁶⁴ UZ Leuven (n.d.) The importance of data sharing. Available at: <https://www.uzleuven.be/en/privacy-and-your-patient-record/importance-data-sharing> (accessed 12 November 2024).

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population groups, including vulnerable groups who face specific (ethical) challenges, to ensure no one is excluded. If needed, information and communication should be multilingual to avoid misunderstandings between professionals and citizens, and in any case, it should address and include people with different social, educational, and cultural backgrounds.

Lastly, and in line with transparency and traceability, patients and citizens mention that, to the extent that this is feasible, communication and the information provided regarding genomic data reuse should be adapted to people's communication and engagement preferences. For instance, not all data subjects have equal needs or preferences in active involvement regarding data governance. Some people prefer being less active or not active at all in health data governance, for instance because they trust professionals in the beneficial reuse of data, they are not interested in data governance, or they fear being overwhelmed with information. Others want to be informed about actual cases of genomic data reuse, but only to a certain degree, for instance when the purpose of genomic data reuse changes significantly. This is particularly applicable if the new purpose is conflicting with the initial purpose of data collection. In this case, people might reconsider their consent. Finally, some patients and citizens want to play an active role in genomic data reuse and governance, for instance by being able to access detailed information on specific cases of reuse or by being able to contribute to policy decisions. Also, and even though basic knowledge about genomics and data reuse is a prerequisite for transparency, people have different preferences regarding the amount of information provided. Hence, a middle ground should be found between providing too little information (which might lead to patients' and citizens' feeling of losing control over sensitive data) and providing too much information (which might overwhelm patients and citizens). In that sense, the legal framework plays a central role in defining controllers' responsibilities towards data subjects and supporting their empowerment in data governance without overburdening clinicians and researchers.

Raising Societal Awareness

On a broader societal level, patients and citizens as well as Can.Heal professionals insist on the need to develop a general awareness about genomics and genomic data reuse. This is essential to ensure more effective collaboration and communication between patients and healthcare professionals, but also to empower lay people in becoming autonomous and responsible actors in their health management (to the extent that they want) .

Can.Heal professionals endorse the importance of improving the genetic literacy of citizens, yet they also recognize how challenging this task can be. They notice how difficult it might already be to explain basic concepts, such as the difference between panel, exome, and genome sequencing and the different consequences these types of testing might have for patients.

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On their side, patients and citizens underline the importance of explaining both the possibilities and limitations of genomic data. Regarding the limitations, they consider it critical to be aware of the uncertainties that are part of or can be caused by genomic information, such as the notions of risk and genetic predisposition (probabilities in disease development), the possibility of variants of uncertain significance, and the impact of evolving scientific knowledge on data interpretation. Moreover, and in line with one of the priorities identified by Can.Heal professionals, lay people pinpoint the need to tackle the deterministic conception of genomics, which can induce a false sense of control over health and might result in inadequate decisions. The complex nature of genomics, combined with its inherent uncertainties, can trigger feelings of confusion and anxiety among patients and citizens, leading to a sense of disempowerment. If, for instance, genomic sequencing results are inconclusive on a disease's manifestation or severity, people might not know which actions are suitable to take or how to communicate about these results to their relatives. However, the extent to which feelings of uncertainty and disempowerment might occur depends on various factors, including the way professionals communicate genomic test results. Hence, the impact of genomic information on citizens and patients is partly defined by counseling procedures.

Additionally, also the possibilities offered by genomic knowledge should be explained to patients and citizens. The actionability of genomic data can empower people, for instance, by allowing them to take preventive or curative (medical) actions or adjust their lifestyle. Hence, this actionability could be a strong argument in favor of knowing genomic test results. However, patients and citizens as well as professionals also acknowledge that the concept of actionability might be unclear, particularly since experts do not seem to reach a general consensus on its definition. Whereas actionability might refer to clinical interventions and the possibility of treating or preventing illness, it might as well include personal utility, such as lifestyle or personal adjustments.

Discussion on Ethical Implications and Resulting Recommendations

Definitions and Alignment

The reuse of genomic data for clinical purposes can harness the power and opportunities of genomic data beyond individual cases of care. It can inform clinical interpretations and decisions and, consequently, support and improve the clinical care of many (other and/or future) patients.

However, throughout the discussions with Can.Heal professionals, it was noteworthy that not all professionals share the same definition regarding genomic data reuse. Whether a certain practice is considered to fall within the scope of this definition, depends on elements such as the amount and types of data that are available or suitable for reuse (the entire dataset, summarized data, de-identified

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data, etc.), the clinical similarity between the initial sequencing context and the context of reuse (addressing a similar or different disease), and the person who might benefit from this reuse (the initial data subject, relatives, patients with a similar disease, patients in general). As an example, some Can.Heal professionals indicated that consulting a database of genomic variants to support variant classification is not considered actual reuse. In the BALLETT study⁶⁵, for instance, genomic sequencing data are maintained in a publicly available database that might be consulted for variant classification in other clinical cases and/or by other professionals. Nevertheless, practices like these are not considered actual reuse since the scope of available data is considered too limited. In the BALLETT dataset, only somatic variants in about 500 cancer-related genes are taken into account. Such a dataset is considered too limited for reuse in the sense of reinterrogating these sequences with the aim of identifying variants that might be clinically relevant in other clinical cases. Additionally, it was mentioned that not only genomic data reuse might be hard to define and delineate but that, along with this, the data under consideration are also a moving target. Depending on the specific clinical context, the scope of data that can be reused, differs. If genomic data are reused to potentially benefit the initial data subject (the index person) or their relatives, it might be possible to reuse all available data. The underlying reason lies in current consent procedures that often cover this type of data reuse for future care of the data subject and their relatives. If, however, genomic data would be reused to support the clinical care of unrelated persons or to address questions regarding unrelated diseases, only a subset of the available data or only summarized data might be reused and this because of regulations such as the principle of data minimisation.

Hence, both the definition of genomic data reuse for clinical purposes and the scope of data that can be included in this reuse are unclear. Additionally, current governance systems often treat clinical care and research and as two distinct contexts and separable activities. However, many activities within the domain of genomic medicine and genomic data reuse occur within a hybrid and fluent space between those two. Genomic data reuse for clinical purposes might be one of the best examples. Genomic data, often collected within a clinical context, are used for research activities that have, nevertheless, a primary aim of finding a clinical diagnosis, for instance for patients with a rare disease. In such a situation, regulations and governance structures (that are often only applicable within one context) might challenge rather than support ethical practice⁶⁶.

⁶⁵ The BALLETT study serves as a use case within the WP10 Oncology Decision Support Tools of Can.Heal. It is a comprehensive sequencing study that examines the value of broad agnostic NGS panel testing versus organ-directed NGS. More information on the BALLETT study and its inclusion as a use case within Can.Heal is available via <https://canheal.eu/wp10-oncology-decision-support-tools/> and <https://www.bsмо.be/news/precision-initiative-two-ongoing-comprehensive-genomic-profiling-studies-from-bsмо-geneo-and-ballett/> (both accessed 12 November 2024).

⁶⁶ Horton and Lucassen (2023).

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Many different elements (the disease under consideration, the persons who might benefit from reuse, the clinical versus research context, etc.) affect whether professionals consider a certain practice to fall within the scope of actual reuse. Such conceptual and practical vagueness is detrimental to correct practice. It leads to a potential misalignment between professionals but also between professionals and patients. It blurs the scope of regulations and creates uncertainty regarding the information that should be communicated, the concerns and values that are at stake, the regulations that should be respected and the good clinical practice that should be pursued. Summarized, without a clear definition, the area in which reuse takes place and must be carried out and regulated as optimally as possible (practically, legally, ethically speaking), is undetermined.

Recommendation 4 - *As a prerequisite for the development of an ethical framework for genomic data reuse for clinical purposes, the meaning and scope of this type of reuse need to be defined and delineated as well as possible. Professional definitions need to be aligned to optimize professional interactions (also between the clinical and the research context), apply relevant regulations and frameworks correctly, and inform and involve patients and citizens accurately.*

Genomic Data as Individual and Collective Entity

The reuse of genomic data for clinical purposes highlights the nature of genomic data as both individual and collective, as well as the potential tension between autonomous decision-making by patients and citizens and professional duties. When the condition of mutual trust is met, a practice of shared decision-making might be able to simultaneously respect the values of patients and citizens and fulfill professional duties, so decisions on genomic data reuse become a shared responsibility. Nevertheless, the particular translation of shared decision-making into practice strongly depends on people's personal preferences, possibilities and context. While some patients prefer not to have an active role in their health data management and, instead, trust their caregiver's and assign responsibility to them regarding appropriate decision-making, others want to be involved more actively. Lay people and professionals should negotiate and agree upon the particular interpretation of shared decision-making in a specific context, so everyone's roles and responsibilities are clearly defined.

Recommendation 5 - *Patients and citizens should be informed about the individual and collective value of genomic data. On the one hand, they should be informed about the possibilities to be involved in genomic data reuse and the ways to be respected in their personal preferences. On the other hand, it is important to foster the values of altruism and solidarity. Together with their healthcare professionals, they should agree upon the particular interpretation of shared decision-making regarding the reuse of genomic data and the extent to which they want to take an active role in this.*

Consent Procedures

At the time the data subject provides their data within the context of genomic sequencing, it is very difficult to define the future ways in which these data will actually be reused. The value of genomic data is highly evolving, the potential uses and the resulting insights and consequences are hard to predict, and, more generally, the uncertainties regarding genomic data and their reuse, are numerous. Hence, consent to the reuse of genomic data (for clinical but also for research and public health purposes) cannot possibly be specific and, instead, will always be open-ended to some extent⁶⁷.

Alternatives to one-time specific consent, such as dynamic, tiered, and broad consent, allow people to reconsider their consent decisions over time. However, the practical implementation of these forms of opt-in consent approaches remains challenging. Questions include issues such as the most feasible way of recontacting patients and citizens over time, the most effective way of providing information, finding the right balance between respect for people's autonomy and the collective value of genomic data reuse (for instance, for research or policymaking), etc.

Due to the challenges related to explicit opt-in approaches in consent, many Can.Heal professionals suggested an opt-out system in which genomic data can be reused for particular purposes (such as academic research or public health) by default, except when the data subject chooses to opt out of this reuse. Opt-out consent might be the best compromise to respect patients' autonomy and values while supporting clinical, research, and public health benefits thanks to effective genomic data reuse. Moreover, opt-out procedures might facilitate interactions between the clinical and research context and enhance data flows from one context to the other. This way, opt-out procedures could maximize the societal value of genomic data⁶⁸. In line with this support for opt-out consent systems, also the current EHDS Legislative Proposal foresees an opt-out option for the processing of personal electronic health data for secondary use. Nevertheless, several exceptions to this right to opt out apply, for instance when data are reused for purposes regarding scientific research for important reasons of public interest⁶⁹.

Choosing for a system of opt-out instead of opt-in consent should not be misinterpreted as a *carte blanche* for genomic data users. The possibility to opt out in a system of genomic data reuse by default does not equate to allowing any kind of reuse but rather imposes great responsibility on data users to thoroughly consider every case of reuse and align it with the data subjects' values and concerns⁷⁰.

⁶⁷ Horton and Lucassen (2023).

⁶⁸ Kilgus et al. (2024).

⁶⁹ EHDS (n.d.). The European Health Data Space. Available at: <https://www.european-health-data-space.com/> (accessed 13 November 2024).

⁷⁰ Horton and Lucassen (2023).

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Maintaining the option to opt-out of genomic data reuse and, hence, to provide consent regarding the reuse of one’s personal and sensitive data, is an essential tool to support and encourage the involvement of patients and citizens. Even though consent might be problematic as a legal basis for genomic data reuse⁷¹, it certifies its value as good clinical practice. Irrespective of the legal feasibility of consent, providing the possibility of an opt-out confirms both citizens’ and professionals’ idea of consent as an agreement between data subjects and data users beyond legal obligations. It enables patients’ and citizens’ values to be respected without limiting the power of data reuse and it materializes the fundamental relationship that is established between data subjects and data users in any case of reuse. Even though a legal requirement of consent might not be recommended, it is of utmost importance to establish feasible ways to still enable consent as an ethical practice that embodies trust between the different stakeholders within the field of genomic data reuse.

Recommendation 6 - *To respect patients’ and citizens’ values while supporting the benefits of genomic data reuse for clinical but also research and public health purposes, effective consent procedures including opt-out options should be developed. This consent should not solely be considered a legal requirement but an ethical agreement that enables and supports public involvement in genomic data reuse and that materializes trust between all stakeholders.*

Understanding Genomic data Reuse

Patients, citizens and Can.Heal professionals all emphasize the need for a better understanding and an increased societal awareness regarding genomic medicine and, more specifically, genomic data reuse. From an ethico-legal point of view, it is important to underline that providing information to data subjects is not only good practice in a clinical and ethical way, but also a legal requirement within the General Data Protection Regulation⁷².

By providing transparent information, patients and citizens should become aware of the value and power of genomic data to increase scientific knowledge and improve healthcare. Highlighting the common good that can be realized by genomic data reuse and creating a supportive societal culture are important and effective ways to facilitate and encourage genomic data sharing⁷³⁻⁷⁴.

Despite this link between transparency, trust, societal support, and a willingness towards data sharing, it is very important to recognise that transparency as well as the resulting trust should not be

⁷¹ See the section on “Suitable Legal Bases for Genomic data Sharing - Consent” in the Can.Heal Deliverable D12.1 – Ethical and legal compliance recommendations for data governance.

⁷² See the section on *Data Subjects’ Rights - Right to be informed* in the Can.Heal Deliverable D12.1 – Ethical and legal compliance recommendations for data governance.

⁷³ Horton and Lucassen (2023).

⁷⁴ Bilodeau et al. (2024).

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considered mere tools towards a social acceptance and willingness of data sharing. Transparency about genomic data reuse should not succumb to an instrumentalist or even propagandist approach but, instead, it should clearly describe and explain practices of reuse, such as for clinical or research purposes, so patients and citizens can evaluate themselves whether and how (under which conditions) these types of reuse are socially acceptable and trustworthy⁷⁵.

Therefore, transparency as well as the information provided to improve societal awareness and genetic literacy require to highlight not only the potential benefits of genomic data reuse but also its limitations, risks, and uncertainties⁷⁶. Data users should be honest about, for instance, the possibilities and limitations regarding the de-identification of genomic data and about data protection measures and the potential risk of data misuse⁷⁷.

Recommendation 7 - *Patients and citizens should be more aware and better informed about the value of genomic data reuse. The information provided should be transparent and honest, highlighting both the possibilities and limitations of genomic medicine. The power and actionability as well as the uncertainties of genomic data should be equally addressed. This transparency allows for the establishment of trust between patients, citizens, and professionals, which might contribute to a societal culture supportive of genomic data reuse. Societal trust and support can result in an increased willingness to share genomic data, although this should not be a pursued goal but the result of trustworthy practices.*

Information should not only be transparent and honest but also accessible, adjusted to different information and communication preferences, and adjusted to different population groups⁷⁸.

Various ways of making complex clinical information more accessible and understandable have been explored. For instance, the Belgian communication tool BabbleBoost uses visual materials to better align healthcare provision with people's preferences, needs and priorities and to improve patient-centered care⁷⁹. To make information as comprehensible as possible to the general population, patients and citizens could also be involved in the development of educational tools and training programmes⁸⁰.

⁷⁵ Bilodeau et al. (2024).

⁷⁶ King Baudouin Foundation (2020). ZOOM: Caring technology. Report, King Baudouin Foundation, Belgium, October.

⁷⁷ Horton and Lucassen (2023).

⁷⁸ Bilodeau et al. (2024).

⁷⁹ BRUSANO (n.d.). Aide à la consultation: BabbelBoost. Available at: <https://www.brusano.brussels/service/babbelboost/> (accessed 14 November 2024).

⁸⁰ Kreeftenberg, Henneman, Ket, et al. (2024).

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To effectively inform and sensitize patients and citizens about genomic data reuse, it is important to provide the right amount of information. On the one hand, enough and honest information should be provided. As mentioned above, information on genomic data reuse should not be limited to its strengths and potential benefits but should also address its limitations, risks and uncertainties. Only this way, patients and citizens will be able to make informed decisions that truly align with their personal values. On the other hand, people should not be overwhelmed with information. Providing the most relevant information on genomic data reuse, such as information regarding data users, purposes of reuse and data protection measures, can be sufficient to establish trust⁸¹. Trust requires assurance (by transparent information) that genomic data reuse aligns with people’s preferences and values and follows predefined conditions but it does not equate excessively detailed information.

Different people will have different preferences regarding the amount of information provided as well as regarding the degree of involvement in genomic data reuse and governance. The information provided to patients and citizens should address these diverse preferences to the extent possible, for instance by offering different levels and different types of information. Also the degree of preferred involvement could be addressed by offering more active or passive roles in genomic data governance. In any case, and to align the expectations of lay people and professionals, it should be clear which types of involvement (for instance, consulting general information, following up on specific cases of reuse, exercising control over genomic data reuse, etc.) are available in specific types or cases of reuse. It is important to note that the aspiration of some citizens to become more active partners in genomic data reuse does not equal a barrier to efficient data accessibility and reuse. Citizens and patients do not want to impede progress within personalized medicine, yet they want personalized medicine to evolve in line with their central values. Improved transparency and involvement in data reuse can be a win-win situation in which data subjects witness how researchers or clinicians reuse their data for the benefit of others, which, in turn, could stimulate their willingness to contribute even more.

Finally, information about genomic data reuse should be adjusted to different population groups. Special attention should be given to vulnerable and underprivileged people, so genomic data reuse and innovation might reduce the health gap rather than reinforcing it⁸².

Recommendation 8 - *Public information about genomic data reuse should be accessible and personalized to the extent possible. It should be adjusted to different population groups, as well as to people’s preferences regarding communication and involvement. Hence, different communication and*

⁸¹ Bilodeau et al. (2024).

⁸² King Baudouin Foundation (2020).

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involvement tools (such as visuals tools, interactive platforms, citizen engagement opportunities, etc.) should be available.

Incidental and Secondary Findings in the Reuse of Genomic Data

Introduction

Whole-exome and genome sequencing, but also the analysis of large gene panels may lead to the identification of clinically relevant findings that go beyond the initial aim of sequencing. The identification of these additional findings may occur in the clinical, research, or public health context.

Additional findings can be identified by accident. Even though these *incidental findings* (IFs) are discovered accidentally, they can be clinically relevant by-products of sequencing. Or, additional findings can also be pursued on purpose. These *secondary findings* (SFs) can be considered a way of opportunistic screening.

IFs and SFs can reveal serious health risks and require referral for further follow-up of the initially tested person (the index person) and eventually of their relatives, depending on the specific result. The most common type of incidental finding in oncogenomics is the discovery of germline pathogenic variants in cancer cells. Several guidelines exist on the disclosure of genomic IFs and SFs, such as the recommendations of the American College of Medical Genetics and Genomics (ACMG)⁸³, the European Society of Human Genetics (ESHG)⁸⁴, and the European Society for Medical Oncology Precision Medicine Working Group (ESMO PMWG)⁸⁵. Despite these recommendations, reporting IFs and SFs remains a challenging task because of result interpretation but also because of ethical and legal issues, such as informed consent, professional confidentiality, counseling, and family impact.

In the Can.Heal use cases that have been performed, and more generally in the European cancer genomic platform to be established, there is no doubt that IFs will be identified regularly. Moreover, it should be discussed if, and under which conditions, SFs should be pursued in the context of platform-based sequencing activities. Hence, contributing to the development of a feasible, clinically effective but also ethically sound policy regarding the disclosure of IFs and SFs towards patients and citizens is one of the main objectives of WP12.

Individual versus Systemic Impact of Incidental and Secondary Findings

Generally, the lay public citizens and professionals approach IFs and SFs rather differently. While patients and citizens put an emphasis on the individual impacts of additional genomic findings,

⁸³ Green RC, Berg JS, Grody WW, et al. (2013) ACMG recommendations for reporting of incidental findings in clinical exome and genome sequencing. *Genetics in medicine* 15.7: 565-574.

⁸⁴ Van El CG, Cornel MC, Borry P, et al. (2013) Whole-genome sequencing in health care. *European Journal of Human Genetics*, 21(6), 580-584.

⁸⁵ Kuzbari Z, Bandlamudi C, Loveday C, et al. (2023) Germline-focused analysis of tumour-detected variants in 49,264 cancer patients: ESMO Precision Medicine Working Group recommendations. *Annals of Oncology* 34.3: 215-227.

Can.Heal professionals are mainly concerned about the systemic impacts of these findings, i.e. their repercussions on the healthcare system.

FIGURE 7 - Impact of incidental and secondary findings

Citizens and patients mainly focus on the individual, personal impact of potential IFs. They consider this impact to depend on several factors. First, it depends on the clinical characteristics of the IF, including elements such as the specific disease the IF is associated with, the chance that this disease might actually manifest itself (i.e. penetrance), the severity of the disease, and the existence or absence of preventive or curative measures. Second, the impact of IFs depends on the personal context of patients, including their living and family situation and their family history of disease. People's specific living and family situation might, for instance, affect which preventive, reproductive or other measures related to the particular IF and its associated disease, might be useful or feasible for someone. Finally, also genetic counseling, including the way risks related to IFs are presented and the focus that is put on, for instance, preventive options, affects the impact of IFs. Depending on this estimated meaning and impact of IF on patients, IFs are expected to have an empowering or disempowering effect. In case of empowerment, patients and citizens mainly think about how they might take certain actions based on this additional knowledge, such as exploring or deciding on preventive or curative options, informing family members about potential clinical risks, adjusting their life to potential future health problems, or preparing psychologically for possible illness. When thinking about disempowering effects of IFs, patients and citizens refer to the absence of preventive or curative options, the overwhelming effect and psychological harm of receiving information about a disease risk, and the uncertainty surrounding IFs. Indeed, the exact meaning of an IF (and of a genetic variant in general) is not always certain since its clinical significance or penetrance might be unclear or its severity might be variable.

The personal impact of IFs prompts many people to the idea that they should be the ones deciding about the disclosure of IFs. Patients and citizens consider themselves best suited to estimate the potential empowering or disempowering impact of an IF on their lives and the lives of family members. Hence, most want to be respected in their autonomy and, consequently, they often defend a right to know but also not to know IFs. Nevertheless, given the potential impact of IFs on relatives, some patients and citizens defend that family members have an equal right to know or not to know IFs and, hence, they should also be considered in the decision taken by the index person. Despite the emotional distress of informing relatives and the fear of damaging intimate relationships, some judge that the responsibility of offering relatives the chance for prevention and faster diagnosis should prevail.

When reflecting on IFs on a less personal and more societal level, many patients and citizens think that these additional sequencing results might be of value for scientific purposes. Even if people do not want to be informed about them, doing further research on these findings might lead to

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improvements in medicine and public health. However, patients and citizens do not largely elaborate on this, highlighting the necessity to further explore how research on IFs and SFs could be valuable in the context of genomic data reuse for clinical purposes to help other patients, even if the index person chooses not to know them.

Unlike most patients' and citizens' emphasis on personal autonomy, Can.Heal professionals questioned whether there sometimes might be a professional responsibility or even duty to report IFs, depending on the specific context. A first element that affects this responsibility concerns the correct pathogenic interpretation of IFs. Genomic variant interpretation is often challenging, especially in the context of IFs since, mostly, no associated phenotype is present. Additionally, when the variant is identified in a research or public health context, where there might be no direct link with the data subject, this variant interpretation might be particularly difficult. Hence, it is imperative to support the development and maintenance of (inter)national databases of variant classification to which all NGS laboratories have access. Such a practice of shared expertise is necessary to facilitate interpretation and reporting decisions to patients and, eventually, their relatives. Secondly, the follow-up of IFs, both towards patients and their relatives, must be guaranteed to ensure that the identification of IFs actually equals a higher identification of cancer predispositions compared to the identification based on clinical criteria, which are often limited. Only when this condition is fulfilled, IFs will be an effective additional preventive measure. Thirdly, Can.Heal professionals ask for a clear and, preferably, European legal framework regarding the reporting of IFs. This framework should clarify professional responsibilities and duties and align them with other relevant legislations such as the law on patient rights (which, under specific circumstances, grants patients and citizens the right to obtain certain information such as IFs). Moreover, a European legal framework should help overcome the different country-specific regulations on the reporting of genomic sequencing results, including IFs and SFs.

Within the Can.Heal project, professionals indicate that IFs are a point of concern in several use cases. For instance, in the BALLETT use case, IFs have been reported resulting from germline genetic analyses of cancer susceptibility gene variants. Initially, reporting decisions were made on a case-by-case basis, resulting in the disclosure of IFs to 12% of the patients. Later on, the data have been reanalysed following the ESMO PMWG guidelines, resulting in the reporting of IFs (regarding germline mutations) to 15% of the patients⁸⁶.

Despite this reporting of IFs in this use case, Can.Heal professionals emphasize that, currently, there is a focus on clinically relevant results and, hence, IFs are actually avoided as much as possible.

⁸⁶ Kuzbari et al. (2023).

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Consequently, Can.Heal professionals involved in the use case on biobanking⁸⁷ state that some IFs might not have been reported to patients because of their non-clinical applicability.

However, several Can.Heal professionals comment that, in contrast to the current policy in the use cases, there is a trend in some clinical domains, including oncology, to provide as much information as possible, and hence, to not only report IFs but also actively pursue SFs. This clear distinction between unintentional IFs and intentional SFs and, more particularly, the possibility and upcoming trend of actively looking for SFs, has led to extensive discussions among Can.Heal professionals. Some professionals think that SFs, such as findings related to pharmacogenomics or other types of cancer, should be pursued since such a proactive approach is able to avoid a lot of clinical harm. It is currently estimated that clinically actionable mutations, such as a variant in the BRCA1-gene, would already be identified quite regularly among the general population. With the practice of polygenic risk scores being increasingly used in the future, clinically relevant genomic test results might be identified far more frequently.

Nevertheless, a deliberate hunt for SFs will pose several challenges. Can.Heal professionals mainly focus on the systemic impact that a deliberate search for SFs might have on the healthcare system and on the provision and organization of health care. They strongly emphasize that the current healthcare system is not ready for a deliberate search for SFs. Due to limited healthcare resources and current organizational structures, the active tracking of SFs may lead to issues regarding fairness and the prioritization of care. It could, for instance, lead to longer waiting times for patients to receive primary genetic test results. Moreover, informing patients about the possibility of SFs and/or actually reporting these results will significantly affect and complicate the daily tasks of clinicians and genetic counselors. In line with these ideas, and despite the potential clinical value of actively pursuing SFs, there are currently no additional screenings performed for SFs within the Can.Heal use cases and this mainly for reasons of efficiency and fairness.

As a concluding remark to the ethical discussion on SFs, Can.Heal professionals point out that the decision and policy on whether to pursue SFs or not require a general reflection on the approach to prevention and healthcare we want to pursue. Do we want to be more cautious or even conservative by avoiding IFs and SFs as much as possible? Or do we take a non-conservative stance by actively pursuing SFs and taking the opportunity to increase the detection rate of cancer predispositions? If the last option would be adopted and SFs would become the norm instead of an exception, there might

⁸⁷ Within Can.Heal “WP4 Biobanking - Genome of Europe” aims for the creation and validation of biobanks and (germline) genetic datasets for cancer patient cohorts. More information about WP4 is available via <https://canheal.eu/wp4-biobanking-genome-of-europe/> (accessed 12 November 2024).

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be a need to reevaluate our understanding and definition of central concepts in healthcare, such as prevention, diagnosis, and treatment, and update our conception of what appropriate care means.

Common Interests but Different Interpretations regarding Incidental and Secondary Findings

FIGURE 8 - Common interests, different interpretations regarding incidental and secondary findings

Common Interests, Different Interpretations

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Contrary to the difference between the individual approach of IFs by patients and citizens and the systemic approach of SFs by professionals, lay and expert stakeholders also share some interests regarding additional genomic findings. In these shared interests and concerns, less of a distinction is made between accidentally identified IFs and purposefully pursued SFs. Instead, the concerns apply to the more general idea of additional genomic findings that go beyond the initial reason for sequencing and data reuse, be it in a clinical, research, or public health context.

In the context of interpreting and potentially reporting IFs and SFs, patients, citizens, and Can.Heal professionals all emphasize the importance of three key elements: (1) relatives, (2) informed consent procedures, and (3) genetic counseling. Nevertheless, lay and expert stakeholders differ in the underlying interpretations of these elements.

Relatives

Due to the potentially hereditary factor of IFs and SFs, patients and citizens do not limit the personal impact of these findings to themselves but also consider their possible effect on relatives that might need to be tested or followed-up. The potential impact of IFs and SFs on relatives and the associated possibility or need to warn them to potentially prevent harm, are some of the elements people take into account when considering whether they would or would not like to receive these findings. On the one hand, patients and citizens refer to relatives' right to know IFs and SFs and to be able to avoid potential harm. On the other hand, relatives also have the right not to know IFs and SFs and be respected in their autonomous choices. Moreover, patients might experience the responsibility to inform relatives about IFs and SFs as a very heavy responsibility to carry and, hence, this might be a reason for them not wanting to know IFs or SFs themselves. All these elements regarding the potential family relevance of IFs and SFs might affect people's preferences and decisions regarding the disclosure of IFs and SFs and, hence, they should be addressed and balanced during genetic counseling consults.

On their side, Can.Heal professionals emphasize how the clinical interpretation of an IF/SF might be affected by people's relatives and, more specifically, by their family history of disease. A person's family disease history might support a professional's interpretation and understanding of IFs and SFs, for instance, regarding their pathogenicity and severity.

In sum, patients, citizens, and Can.Heal professionals all highlight the importance of relatives in the context of IFs and SFs, yet they do so in a different stage of the results' interpretation and impact. Whereas professionals focus on the importance of family members before or during the interpretation of IFs and SFs (with a family history of disease as one of the contributing factors for the results' interpretation), patients and citizens mainly focus on the potential importance for family members of

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IFs and SFs after they have been interpreted. Both perspectives are valuable and important to consider since they complement each other in how and when to best approach family implications of extra genomic findings.

Informed Consent

Informed consent is a second shared interest between patients, citizens, and Can.Heal professionals regarding IFs and SFs.

For patients and citizens, informed consent is often viewed as the practical tool to respect autonomy. Being informed about the possibility of IFs and SFs and being allowed to make a personal choice regarding the disclosure of these results allows people to exercise their right to know or not to know. However, in some research studies with clinical implications, including use cases within Can.Heal, professionals inform patients (pre-testing) about the possibility of IFs without offering the possibility of opting out or making personalized choices regarding these findings. Such a policy might, nevertheless, be justified by the specific circumstances of sequencing, such as in the BALLETT study, where sequencing was often offered as a kind of last resort to potentially provide final treatment options (cf. *infra*).

Compared to the alignment that patients and citizens see between autonomy (as the theoretical value) and informed consent options (as the practical tool), professionals are more concerned about the concrete implementation and the practicalities of informed consent procedures. For instance, they wonder if procedures of tiered and/or dynamic consent might be required to address and manage the potential re-interpretation of IFs and SFs over time (that might change the finding's relevance and meaning and, hence, affect people's preferences regarding whether or not to be informed). Also technical adjustments, such as testing larger panels or starting to use polygenic risk scores, might increase the chance of IFs. In current Can.Heal use cases, such technical changes are not addressed during the informed consent procedure, resulting in patients not being informed about those changes. Hence, patients automatically agree to a broader scope of possible results and, hence, a higher probability of IFs.

Counseling

Finally, patients, citizens, and professionals all underline the importance of genetic counseling regarding IFs and SFs.

As mentioned previously, patients and citizens consider counseling an important factor that contributes to the interpretation and potential impact of IFs and SFs, depending on, for instance, the information provided on associated preventive and treatment options. On their side, professionals

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point out the urge for a general awareness on the possibility of IFs and eventually SFs, both among oncogenomic professionals and the general public. Towards professionals, case studies such as the BALLETT study can help increase awareness in NGS laboratories, yet more general initiatives are required. Towards patients and citizens, Can.Heal professionals recommend that counseling should feature less technical, more easily understandable and accessible, and maybe more gradual ways of providing information. The use of more visual counseling tools and, again, tiered and/or dynamic consent are suggested as possible tools. The practical implementation of counseling strategies is a major concern among Can.Heal professionals, who emphasize the importance of considering carefully how information is best provided to patients.

Regarding the amount and granularity of information provided, specific testing circumstances might be of relevance. For instance, in the BALLETT study it was decided to only provide general information about IFs and this because of the specific context of testing, where sequencing was often offered to possibly provide some last treatment options. In this context, information about IFs is still considered important but less relevant than in other contexts. Generally, it is essential not to overload patients with information regarding both primary results and the possibility of IFs.

Regarding the timing of providing information about the possibility of IFs, Can.Heal professionals consider it convenient to do so at the same time as information is provided about NGS testing in general (pre-testing). However, the reporting of actual IFs might be more suitable after diagnostic/somatic results have been discussed. The disclosure of somatic test results is a priority since it is required for decision-making regarding treatment and follow-up. Instead, IFs are generally less relevant and less urgent, apart from some exceptions, such as IFs regarding germline mutations that might be relevant for decisions on the most effective treatment.

Finally, it is important to be considerate about who is communicating information regarding IFs and SFs to patients and citizens and to be clear about their role. In the context of the Can.Heal use case on biobanking, for instance, IFs have been reported to patients not by researchers themselves but by a genetic counselor. Nevertheless, some IFs might have been considered not clinically relevant and, by consequence, they are only mentioned in the lab report yet not communicated to the genetic counselor for further reporting to the patient. It is not clear to which extent genetic counselors are aware of these procedures but, in favor of streamlined counseling procedures, it is important to have transparent guidelines on which stakeholders should be informed about which types of results.

Considerations regarding the most suitable way of counseling patients and citizens about IFs and SFs, including the amount, granularity, and timing of providing information and the role and responsibilities of specific professionals (clinicians, researchers, genetic counselors), suggest that

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counseling procedures require a personalized approach. This way, and despite their focus on the systemic impact of IFs and SFs, professionals also endorse the idea of the personal impact of IFs and SFs.

Discussion on Ethical Implications and Resulting Recommendations

Definitions and Alignment

When addressing the issue of IFs and SFs in genomic data reuse, patients, citizens and professionals share some interests and concerns, such as the relevance of relatives and the importance of effective counseling and consent procedures. Nevertheless, even within these shared interests, they differ in their particular interpretations and emphases. Also on a more overarching level, citizens and professionals approach additional genomic sequencing results from a different and, respectively, more personal or systemic perspective. Whereas different approaches and concerns are not problematic in itself, it is, however, important to ensure that different stakeholders refer to the same things when using the same terms or concepts. Only this way, conversation and interaction can lead to a mutual understanding and, eventually, to an alignment and compatibility of values, interests, needs and concerns.

In the context of genomic IFs and SFs, the need for clear definitions and concepts particularly applies to the terminology of IFs and SFs as such and to the importance of relatives.

Regarding the terminology of IFs and SFs, many debates have taken place to arrive at the most correct terminology possible and, simultaneously, to make a clear distinction between accidentally discovered findings and purposefully pursued additional results. Many Can.Heal professionals clearly and explicitly distinguish between IFs and SFs, whereas patients and citizens do not. A different level of professional versus layman's knowledge and a limited genetic literacy among patients and citizens may easily explain this difference, yet also more fundamental issues might be involved. Patients and citizens mainly focus on the personal impact of additional genomic test results. In this approach, it might not matter whether these results have been identified by accident (IFs) or on purpose (SFs). In contrast, professionals mainly focus on the systemic impact on the healthcare system of a purposeful search for additional genomic sequencing results, which necessitates an explicit differentiation between IFs and SFs. To avoid a misunderstanding between stakeholders concerning different approaches and interests, it is important to create a basic awareness among all of them regarding the different types of additional genomic findings and the different consequences these might have (in terms of, for instance, clinical consequences, counseling, or reimbursement).

The importance of relatives is a shared concern among patients, citizens and professionals in the context of IFs and SFs. For patients and citizens, this interest results from their focus on the personal impact of additional genomic findings. They realize that these results might not only affect themselves but also their (future) relatives and, consequently, this potential family-wide relevance of results may have an impact on whether or not they want to be informed about them. For professionals, however, family members are already relevant before the communication of IFs or SFs, as a person's family history of disease may affect the clinical interpretation of these findings. Patients' and citizens' understanding of the potential family-wide impact of genomic test results (including IFs and SFs) is a valuable entry point to further develop their genetic literacy. It is important to finetune their knowledge and, for instance, explain that relatives (and their history of disease) not only affect the communication and impact of IFs and SFs but also their interpretation and clinical significance. This way, patients' and citizens' expectations might be adjusted and this, for instance, to avoid unexpected situations in which family members are already involved in the sequencing and interpretation process before IFs and SFs have been reported to the index person.

Recommendation 9 - *Genomic sequencing and, more specifically, the potential identification of IFs and SFs, are contexts that are characterized by a complex terminology and a high level of uncertainty. Despite the different stakeholders' various backgrounds and levels of knowledge, aligned definitions (for instance of IFs and SFs) and clear concepts (for instance regarding family relevance) are of utmost importance to realize a true understanding between patients, citizens and professionals. In this alignment, not only terminological issues but also underlying values and concerns (for instance the personal versus systematic impact of genomic test results) should be taken into account.*

Towards a new definition of care?

One of the main ethical questions regarding IFs and SFs is whether and how the identification of these results and, more specifically, the deliberate pursuit of SFs will affect the definition and interpretation of care. The impact of a practice of SFs on the healthcare system and on the interpretation of prevention, diagnostics and treatment should not be underestimated⁸⁸. Screening for SFs will have an impact on the available resources and, hence, might decrease the time and resources spent on primary diagnoses and treatment. This raises issues regarding equity and fairness in healthcare⁸⁹. The actual impact of pursuing SFs will depend on elements such as reimbursement and evolutions in genomic medicine and, hence, it might change over time. However, ethical questions regarding the status of (pre-)patients, a more conservative versus permissive or interventionist

⁸⁸ Comité Consultatif National d'Éthique (2018). Rapport de synthèse du Comité Consultatif National d'Éthique. Opinion du comité citoyen. Report, CCNE, France.

⁸⁹ Horton and Lucassen (2023).

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approach towards health and medicine, or the degree to which risks and uncertainties will be accepted, already require thorough reflection. The ESMO PMWG, for instance, considers four levels of “clinical conservatism” regarding germline follow-up in a subset of tumor-detected variants. The most permissive strategy would lead to a germline follow-up of 11,3% of tumors whereas the most conservative approach would involve a germline follow-up of 5,3% of tumors⁹⁰. A value-based consideration of health, care, and genomic medicine can steer decisions on whether (and if so, under which conditions) SFs should be actively pursued, in a thoughtful way.

Recommendation 10 - *The active pursuit of SFs might have a considerable impact on the healthcare system. To steer decisions and policies in a well-grounded way, ethical reflections on, for instance, the acceptability of uncertainty and risks, the approach towards care and prevention, the status of (pre)patients, and interpretation of values such as equity and fairness, should be further developed.*

Counseling

Finally, the potential discovery of IFs as well as the possibility to actively pursue SFs in genomic sequencing and genomic data reuse, should be explicitly taken into account in counseling procedures. Whereas the possibility of IFs and SFs might be explained within the pre-test counseling session (although there is no general consensus on this), it has been questioned whether the reporting of these findings requires a separate consult. This idea leads to suggestions of providing information in a gradual way and establishing procedures of tiered/layered consent. However, these practices might again affect the limited resources that are available within the healthcare system and, hence, touch upon values such as fairness and equity.

Recommendation 11 - *To adequately inform patients and citizens about the possibilities and potential impact of IFs and SFs, effective yet also fair counseling and consent procedures should be developed. Gradual and tiered approaches might be appropriate, although they should be balanced with practical and ethical concerns.*

In the context of informing patients and citizens about IFs and SFs, the role of genetic counselors is essential. To support their function, high-quality training and education should be available. Additionally, to further facilitate counselors’ role, clearly delineated professional roles and streamlined communication flows between them are essential. Professionals should be aware of each other’s common and clinical practices regarding the analysis, interpretation, and reporting of genomic test results and, more specifically, IFs and SFs. This way, professional roles and responsibilities can

⁹⁰ Kuzbari et al. (2023).

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be clearly delineated while overburdening some (groups of) professionals can be avoided. To streamline and enhance the interaction between the clinical and research context, the professional responsibilities and potential duties regarding the reporting of results (and, in particular, IFs and SFs) should preferably also be aligned. This way, clinicians and researchers might share a uniform responsibility towards patients and citizens.

Recommendation 12 - *Genetic counselors play an important role in informing patients and citizens about the possibility and potential impact of genomic test results. To support and enhance counselors' workflow, their role and responsibilities regarding IFs and SFs, as well as those of other professionals involved in genomic medicine and data reuse, should be clearly defined and aligned.*

Recommendations

Below, the recommendations are summarized that have been developed throughout this deliverable. They are structured in a similar way as the deliverable, yet some recommendations have a more transversal character and apply to the reuse of genomic data in general.

Recommendations regarding privacy in the reuse of genomic data

Recommendation 1 - Data users must be honest and realistic towards lay people regarding the privacy protection of their genomic data in order to remain trustworthy, including the practical risk of re-identification and under which conditions.

Recommendation 2 - Privacy protection measures should be dynamic and context-dependent by assessing the practical risk of re-identification to enable more flexible and effective data reuse in various contexts for the benefit of patients and citizens. Yet, it also implies EU harmonized laws against discrimination and stigmatization at the European level to ensure equality in the protection of data subjects across Member States.

Recommendation 3 - The degree of involvement of lay people in data governance should be context-dependent and dynamic. The higher the risk of re-identification, the more lay people want to be involved because the greater the consequences will be on their lives.

Recommendations regarding the reuse of genomic data for clinical purposes

Recommendation 4 - To optimize professional interaction, apply relevant regulations and frameworks, and accurately inform and involve patients and citizens, the meaning and scope of reuse for clinical purposes need to be defined as well as possible.

Recommendation 5 - Patients and citizens should be made aware of the individual and collective value of genomic data. They should be informed about ways to be respected in their personal preferences as well as about the values of altruism and solidarity.

Recommendation 6 - Effective consent procedures including opt-out options should be developed as an ethical agreement and translation of trust between all stakeholders.

Recommendation 7 - To establish trust between patients, citizens, and professionals, as well as a societal culture supportive of genomic data reuse, transparent and honest information should be provided to patients and citizens.

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Recommendation 8 - Public information about genomic data reuse should be accessible and personalized to the extent possible. Moreover, it should be adjusted to different population groups, as well as to people's preferences regarding communication and involvement.

Recommendations regarding incidental and secondary findings in the reuse of genomic data

Recommendation 9 - Clear definitions and aligned interpretations of IFs and SFs, as well as consideration of the underlying values and concerns, are of utmost importance to realize a true understanding between patients, citizens and professionals.

Recommendation 10 - To steer decisions and policies regarding the active pursuit of SFs, ethical reflections on the societal approach to care and prevention and on the values of equity and fairness should be developed.

Recommendation 11 - Effective yet also feasible and fair counseling and consent procedures regarding the possibilities and potential impact of IFs and SFs should be developed.

Recommendation 12 - The role and responsibilities of genetic counselors and other professionals involved in genomic medicine and data reuse, should be clearly defined and aligned.

Annexes

ANNEX 1: Publications Included in the Literature Review on Public Engagement

Publications About Citizen Engagement Initiatives

Comité Consultatif National d'Éthique (2018). Rapport de synthèse du Comité Consultatif National d'Éthique. Opinion du comité citoyen. Report, CCNE, France.

Facio FM, Eidem H, Fisher T, et al. (2013). Intentions to receive individual results from whole-genome sequencing among participants in the ClinSeq study. *European Journal of Human Genetics* 21 (3): 261-265.

Hopkins H, Kinsella S, and Evans G (2021). Implications of whole genome sequencing for newborn screening: A public dialogue. Report, Hopkins Van Mil, UK.

Hoxhaj I, Stojanovic J, and Boccia S (2020). European citizens' perspectives on direct-to-consumer genetic testing: An updated systematic review. *European Journal of Public Health* 33 (5): 947-953.

Ipsos MORI (2019). A public dialogue on genomic medicine: Time for a new social contract? Report, Ipsos MORI, UK.

Lynch F, Meng Y, Best S, et al. (2023). Australian public perspectives on genomic data governance: Responsibility, regulation, and logistical considerations. *European Journal of Human Genetics* 32 (3): 295-301.

Mayeur C and Van Hoof W (2020). My DNA, everybody's business? Qualitative analysis of the Belgian citizen forum on the use of genomic information. Report, Sciencano, Belgium.

Mayeur C, Saelaert M, and Van Hoof W (2021). The Belgian DNA debate: An online deliberative platform on the ethical, legal, and social issues of genomics. *Public Health Genomics* 24 (3-4): 149-159.

Mayeur C and Van Hoof W (2021). Citizens' conceptions of the genome: Related values and practical implications in a citizen forum on the use of genomic information. *Health Expectations* 24 (2): 468-477.

Mayeur C, Mertes H, and Van Hoof W (2023). Do genomic passports leave us more vulnerable or less vulnerable? Perspectives from an online citizen engagement. *Humanities & Social Sciences Communications* 10 (83).

Middleton A, Milne R, Thorogood A, et al. (2019). Attitudes of publics who are unwilling to donate DNA data for research. *European Journal of Medical Genetics* 62 (5): 316-323.

Middleton A, Milne R, Howard H. et al. (2020). Members of the public in the USA, UK, Canada and Australia expressing genetic exceptionalism say they are more willing to donate genomic data. *European Journal of Human Genetics* 28: 424-434.

Middleton A, Adams A, Aidid H, et al. (2023) Public engagement with genomics. *Wellcome Open Research* 8: 310.

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Mosconi P, Castellani C, Villani W, et al. (2015). Cystic fibrosis: To screen or not to screen? Involving a citizens' jury in decisions on screening carrier. *Health Expectations* 18 (6): 1956-1967.

Mosconi P, Colombo C, Satolli R, et al. (2016). Involving a citizens' jury in decisions on individual screening for prostate cancer. *PLoS One* 11 (1): e0143176.

Mosconi P, Colombo C, Roberto A, et al. (2018). Deciding on cystic fibrosis carrier screening: Three citizens' juries and an online survey. *European Journal of Public Health* 28 (5): 973-977.

National Genome Center Denmark (2022). Genetic Analysis. Investigation of Danes' knowledge, attitudes and behavior in relation to genetic analyses. Unpublished advice.

Regier DA, Peacock SJ, Pataky R, et al. (2015). Societal preferences for the return of incidental findings from clinical genomic sequencing: A discrete-choice experiment. *CMAJ* 187 (6): E190-E197.

TEHDAS (2021). Exploratory literature review - Citizens' perceptions of and involvement in health data secondary use and sharing in Europe. Unpublished report.

TEHDAS (2022). Healthy Data, an online citizen consultation about health data reuse – Intermediate report.

TEHDAS (2023). Qualitative study to assess citizens' perception of sharing health data for secondary use and recommendations on how to engage citizens in the EHDS. Report.

Voigt TH, Holtz V, Niemiec E, et al. (2020). Willingness to donate genomic and other medical data: Results from Germany. *European Journal of Human Genetics* 28: 1000-1009.

Publications About Patient Engagement Initiatives

Bennette CS, Trinidad SB, Fullerton SM, et al. (2013). Return of incidental findings in genomic medicine: Measuring what patients value - Development of an instrument to measure preferences for information from next-generation testing (IMPRINT). *Genetics in Medicine* 15 (11): 873-881.

Bijlsma RM, Wouters RH, Wessels H, et al. (2018). Managing unsolicited findings in genomics: A qualitative interview study with cancer patients. *Psycho-Oncology* 27 (4): 1327-1333.

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Bishop CL, Strong KA, and Dimmock DP (2017). Choices of incidental findings of individuals undergoing genome wide sequencing, a single center's experience. *Clinical Genetics* 91 (1): 137-140.

Bombard Y, Veenstra G, Friedman JM, et al. (2009). Perceptions of genetic discrimination among people at risk for Huntington's disease: A cross sectional survey. *BMJ* 338: b2175.

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Christenhusz GM, Devriendt K, Peeters H, et al. (2014). The communication of secondary variants: Interviews with parents whose children have undergone array-CGH testing. *Clinical Genetics* 86 (3): 207-216.

Christenhusz GM, Devriendt K, Van Esch H, et al. (2015). Focus group discussions on secondary variants and next-generation sequencing technologies. *European Journal of Medical Genetics* 58 (4): 249-257.

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Deliverable 12.2 – Citizen and Patient Perspectives on Oncogenomic Data Reuse

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ANNEX 2: Can.Heal Ethics Workshop - Agenda

Workshop

Ethical & legal issues

Tuesday, October 17th
14.00-17.00

14.00-14.15	Introduction
14.15-14.30	Overview of ethical and legal outcomes from patient and citizen engagement initiatives
14.30-14.40	Topic 1 – Anonymization Presentation of public engagement outcomes
14.40-15.10	Interactive discussion
15.10-15.20	Break
15.20-15.30	Topic 2 – Incidental findings Presentation of public engagement outcomes
15.30-16.00	Interactive discussion
16.00-16.10	Topic 3 – Reuse for clinical purposes Presentation of public engagement outcomes
16.10-16.40	Interactive discussion
16.40-16.55	Reflections by Adrian Thorogood and Pascal Borry
16.55-17.00	Next steps